

Highlights

Experimental research on the countercurrent fixed-bed combustion of biomass – A review

Handel A. Martinez–Sarache, Vitor C. Simões, João A. F. Altoé, Juan Jesús Rico, David Patiño Villas, Waldir A. Bizzo

- Comprehensive analysis of biomass combustion in countercurrent fixed-bed systems
- Flexibility of fixed-bed reactors to efficiently burn various biomass types
- Experimental research offers insights into key parameters affecting combustion
- Impact of particle morphology on combustion behaviour emphasizing fuel properties
- Recognition of research gaps and directions to enhance biomass combustion technology

Experimental research on the countercurrent fixed-bed combustion of biomass – A review

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Abstract

Fixed-bed combustion is the oldest and most flexible method for heat generation from solid fuels with diverse morphological characteristics. This approach consolidates countercurrent fixed-bed burners as the most employed technique for biomass combustion in small- and medium-scale installations. In recent decades, researchers worldwide have generated significant experimental evidence to decipher the complex mechanisms behind reaction front propagation using laboratory-scale burners, which simulate the conditions experimented by the fuel in industrial plants. However, abundant information is still dispersed in the specialized literature. Organization is necessary for a critical approach to the state-of-the-art to identify gaps for future research. This paper presents a systematic review of the available literature concerning experimental studies of biomass fixed-bed combustion in laboratory-scale reactors. The central discussion encompasses the definition of the parameters employed to characterize the reaction zone behaviour and their dependence on fuel properties and primary air conditions. The insights gained in this

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revision were addressed to propose criteria for harnessing the abundant availability of agricultural residues as alternative fuels in grate-firing systems.

Keywords: biomass, combustion, fixed bed, countercurrent, experimental research

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Nomenclature

$[A/F]$ Air-to-fuel ratio

$[A/F]_{sto}$ Air-to-fuel ratio at stoichiometric conditions

$[X]$ Average concentration of the gas specie x [%vol.] or [ppmV]

δ Reaction zone thickness [m]

$\dot{m}''_{a,cr}$ Critical air flux [$kg\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}$]

\dot{m}''_a Air flux [$kg\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}$]

\dot{m}''_{bur} Burning rate [$kg\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}$]

$\dot{m}''_{ig,sto}$ Ignition rate at stoichiometric conditions [$kg\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}$]

\dot{m}''_{ig} Ignition rate [$kg\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}$]

λ Stoichiometric ratio

λ_{cr}	Stoichiometric ratio at the critical airflow rate
ω	Moisture level
ϕ	Bed porosity
ρ_b	Bulk density [$kg\ m^{-3}$]
ρ_p	Particle density [$kg\ m^{-3}$]
A_{bed}	Cross-section surface of the fixed bed [m^2]
Bi	Biot number
d_p	Particle diameter [m]
d_s	Particle surface diameter [m]
d_{sv}	Particle surface-volume diameter [m]
dm/dt	Mass loss rate [$kg\ s^{-1}$]
H_i	Height above the grate for position i [m]
N_T	Number of temperature measurement ports along the bed
$t(T_{ref})_i$	Time when T_{ref} is measured at position i [s]
T_{max}	Maximum bed combustion temperature [$^{\circ}C$]
T_{ref}	Reference temperature for ignition front velocity estimation [$^{\circ}C$]
t_{tot}	Total experimental time [s]
v_{ig}	Ignition front propagation velocity [$m\ s^{-1}$]

H/C Hydrogen–Carbon ratio

HHV Higher heating value [$kJ\ kg^{-1}$]

O/C Oxygen–Carbon ratio

VM/FC Ratio between fuel contents of volatile-material and fixed-carbon

1. Introduction

In some industrialized countries, solid biomass represents approximately 15% of electricity generation, such as in Finland, Denmark and Estonia, or between 5% and 10%, which is the case in the United Kingdom, Sweden and Brazil. The use of solid biomass for heating has grown in countries utilizing district heating (Denmark, Estonia, Sweden Finland) to replace fossil fuels [1] and in industrial processes, such as in Germany [2]. Historically, biomass has been the oldest primary energy source known to humanity, and is used as fuel to produce thermal energy by direct combustion. The benefits of biomass as an energy source have encouraged governments to implement policies to increase biomass participation in their national energy mix. These policies promote the exploration of new biomasses, mainly from agro-industrial activities.

In 2019, 9.37% of the primary energy supplied on the planet came from biomass sources [3]. However, this renewable resource is currently underutilized through modern applications to produce energy at a large scale. Among the available solid fuel combustion technologies, fixed-bed reactors present greater flexibility to burn different granulometries and lower operational and installation investments [4, 5]. Although fixed-bed systems dom-

20 inated coal-burning technologies during the first part of the 20th century,
21 their implementation in large-scale plants ($> 150 \text{ MW}_{th}$) for heat generation
22 is currently obsolete [4, 6]. However, many units are still installed around
23 the world, mainly for biomass combustion.

24 The operational activities of traditional fossil fuel-powered facilities for
25 heat and power generation are affected by fuel availability and cost. Under
26 these conditions, waste disposal from raw material processing and human
27 activities may be consolidated as a profitable alternative for fuel procura-
28 tion. Some industries, such as charcoal, sugarcane ethanol, and palm oil, use
29 residual biomass from their processes to produce heat and meet their energy
30 requirements [7]. The surplus energy is usually sold to the local electric net-
31 work. For example, in Brazil, just in 2020, 6.0% of the electricity supplied
32 came from sugarcane processing plants [8], which use residual bagasse to
33 power steam generators. However, the biomass employed in agro-industrial
34 processes is present only after harvest. Therefore, the installed combustion
35 units intended to burn this biomass have a period of inactivity during the
36 year. Integrating new biomass sources for combustion in fixed-bed units
37 would allow continuous operation throughout the year, increasing energy
38 generation with low environmental impact.

39 Inside a combustion chamber, the combustion process must ensure that
40 the best performance includes high combustion efficiency and low emission
41 of pollutants and particulate matter. To achieve this objective, the operative
42 parameters – the airflow rate, primary-secondary air distribution, and fuel
43 residence time – must be maintained during the time in which the fuel is
44 present in the furnace. Ideally, the best operational conditions are obtained

45 from direct measurements in the burner after the fuel is exposed to varia-
46 tions in the operating parameters. Nevertheless, there are several technical
47 and economic limitations to taking measurements in industrial installations.
48 Although computational modelling offers detailed insight into the thermo-
49 chemical conversion phenomena of fuel, the consistency and precision of the
50 results depend on data and assumed hypotheses from experimental measure-
51 ments [9–11]

52 Many experimental techniques for the study of solid fuel combustion ex-
53 ist; laboratory-scale fixed-bed reactors have attributes that motivate their
54 application in the characterization of different fuels [12–14]. Fixed-bed re-
55 actors are relevant for their sample size and the conditions emulated during
56 combustion tests, which are close to those observed in industrial installations
57 [15]. These experimental setups allow direct monitoring of the relevant bed
58 combustion parameters, such as the ignition and burning rates.

59 Many publications in the literature report observations from experimen-
60 tal tests of biomass in laboratory-scale fixed-bed reactors. These works have
61 evaluated the fuel combustion behaviour under different combinations of the
62 operational parameters. The results obtained from these works support
63 the current knowledge about (i) ignition front propagation; (ii) pollutant
64 emission; and (iii) particulate matter formation. Additionally, the acquired
65 data provide the basis to validate numerical models. Despite the significant
66 volume of experimental research conducted on the fixed-bed combustion of
67 biomass, the information remains scattered across numerous studies, lacking
68 a comprehensive synthesis. This absence of organization hinders critically
69 approaching the state-of-the-art to identify gaps for future research.

70 Although a lack of revision works concerning biomass combustion in fixed-
71 bed burners has been reported, some researchers have synthesized the tech-
72 nical and numerical aspects of this phenomenon in thermal installations. Yin
73 et al. [9] reviewed biomass combustion in industrial fixed-bed reactors. This
74 paper presents aspects of relevant topics such as equipment description, sec-
75 ondary air supply distribution, ash-related deposition formation, and compu-
76 tational models. Nevertheless, the work lacks a more detailed description of
77 the process inside the bed. Recman and Hájek [16] reviewed the main char-
78 acteristics of laboratory-scale fixed-bed reactors from different installations
79 around the world. In this revision, the authors focused only on technical
80 characteristics. Khodaei et al. [10] presented a summary of the different
81 modelling approaches for fixed-bed biomass combustion at the laboratory
82 scale. This work stands out because it defines relevant properties of bed
83 combustion, such as the consumption rate, ignition front velocity, peak tem-
84 perature, and reaction zone thickness. Dernbecher et al. [11] revised the nu-
85 merical methodologies applied in biomass fixed-bed combustion modelling at
86 different scales. This work distinguishes each subprocess involved in biomass
87 combustion and classifies the approaches adopted to simulate the reactions
88 in the bed zone at different degrees of complexity. However, these works do
89 not offer a consolidated view of experimental findings.

90 This paper systematically reviews the literature on experimental studies
91 of biomass fixed-bed combustion in laboratory-scale reactors. Because most
92 of the current fixed-bed burners for biomass combustion operate in a counter-
93 current regime, we limited the scope of this revision to such a technique. Ini-
94 tially, we employed a search strategy to collect the pertinent literature from

95 databases. Thereafter, we selected only articles related to the following top-
96 ics: biomass combustion, experimental studies in laboratory-scale fixed-bed
97 reactors in the countercurrent regime, and numerical studies accompanied
98 by experimental validation carried out by the same authors. In this review,
99 we synthesize and consolidate the knowledge generated from a phenomemo-
100 logical perspective of the flame propagation process in a biomass fixed-bed.
101 Our systematic approach uniquely categorizes and analyses the experimental
102 methodologies, fuel properties, and operational conditions, offering a com-
103 prehensive perspective not previously available.

104 The content of this review is as follows: First, we describe the combustion
105 process of a solid fuel particle; additionally, we highlight the fundamental dif-
106 ferences between coal and biomass combustion behaviour. Then, we expose
107 the current technologies for solid fuel combustion and their main operative
108 features and limitations. The laboratory-scale fixed-bed reactors are then
109 depicted together with the systems that compound the experimental setup.
110 In the next section, we explain the process of ignition front propagation
111 along a fixed-bed in a countercurrent regime. This section defines the pa-
112 rameters needed to assess the combustion performance and the techniques
113 to determine them from the measurements during the experiments. Later,
114 we discuss the effects of variations in the operational conditions in fixed-bed
115 combustion. This section presents the reported evidence in the publications
116 reviewed. Finally, we share the main conclusions and the detected gaps in
117 the knowledge generated over the decades regarding fixed-bed combustion of
118 biomass.

Figure 1: Solid particle combustion process

119 2. Solid fuel particle combustion

120 Many works in the literature have aimed to follow the evolution of fuel
 121 particles during their combustion in real time . Different experimental tech-
 122 niques as thermogravimetry [17–19], optic pyrometry [20, 21], and high speed
 123 cinematography [22–26] have been used for this purpose. The results demon-
 124 strate that every solid fuel particle goes through sequential phases during its
 125 combustion regardless of the fuel burned. However, the evolution and dura-
 126 tion of each stage depend on the origin and physicochemical characteristics
 127 of the fuel used.

128 Figure 1 illustrates the combustion of a fuel particle inside a high-temperature
 129 environment with similar conditions to those observed in industrial furnaces.
 130 Initially, the particle absorbs heat at a high rate, and its temperature sud-
 131 denly increases until it exceeds the temperature at which the vapour pressure
 132 exceeds the ambient pressure (boiling point), initiating drying of the parti-
 133 cle. Part of the heat transferred to the particle is absorbed as enthalpy of
 134 vaporization of the moisture contained in the particle. Excess thermal en-

135 ergy increases the temperature of the particle to initiate the release of volatile
136 material in the fuel. This process is defined as pyrolysis. During pyrolysis,
137 a cloud composed of combustible gases, soot, and tar surrounds the solid
138 matrix and isolates its contact with the oxygen [20, 21]. The released gases
139 mix with oxygen by diffusion and convection. Owing to the gradual increase
140 in temperature, the gaseous mixture reaches its ignition point, and a homo-
141 geneous flame forms around the particle. Depending on the flow of oxidant
142 present, the flame varies in size and intensity [27, 28]. The heat released
143 by the flame promotes the pyrolysis step in the particle. As each layer in
144 the particle exhausts its volatile content, a carbonaceous material – named
145 char – and ashes remain in the solid matrix. As the release of volatiles
146 prevents oxygen from accessing the carbonaceous matrix, the char does not
147 react with oxygen initially. However, the carbon dioxide and water vapour
148 produced during the reaction reach the char surface, starting reactions. Un-
149 der some conditions, depending on the temperature, oxygen concentration,
150 particle size, and particle motion relative to the volatile cloud, simultane-
151 ous combustion of the char particle and volatiles may occur [20]. When all
152 volatile contents are depleted, the gas cloud size decreases, and eventually,
153 the oxygen comes into contact with the char, starting its oxidation and gasi-
154 fication. This process lasts until the combustible material contained in the
155 particle is consumed.

156 As the temperature of the particle increases, a conversion front appears
157 inside it that propagates from the outermost layers (Figure 1). This front
158 leads each layer through the drying, pyrolysis, and char oxidation stages. The
159 propagation speed of such a front depends on the particle size, its orientation

160 in the airflow [29], and the external conditions, related to the dimensionless
161 parameter Biot number (Bi). The Biot number provides a criterion for any
162 modelling involving transport by convection and diffusion [9, 30–32]. When
163 $Bi < 0.1$, the internal temperature and concentration gradients may be ne-
164 glected, simplifying the problem by a thermally thin particle approach.

165 On the other hand, when $Bi \geq 0$, the particles are considered thermally
166 thick and inner heat diffusion must be considered. The particle thermal
167 behaviour influences the time necessary for complete combustion inside the
168 burner and offers a basis for selecting the most suitable burning technology.

169 Owing to the nature and composition of biomass particles, their combus-
170 tion presents considerable differences compared with the behaviour observed
171 in coal or other solid fuels:

172 - Although some examples of high-volatile bituminous coal exist [33–35],
173 the general trend in the literature shows that biomass has a higher
174 volatile content (60–80%) than coal (20–30%). Consequently, the reac-
175 tion of biomass particles presents a more extended pyrolysis stage that
176 starts at lower temperatures than that of coal particles [19, 21, 36–38].
177 During this phase, the biomass particles release most of their energy
178 content [39]. The high volatile material content in biomass is due to
179 its high molar H/C and O/C ratios. Similarly, the presence of alkali
180 has an impact on the production of volatiles, the reactivity and the
181 production of tar from the particle [40–43]. These elements participate
182 as catalysts in oxidation and pyrolysis reactions, reducing the tempera-
183 tures at which this stage starts and increasing the volatile release rates
184 [44].

- 185 - Although the elevated amount of oxygen bonded to the biomass struc-
186 ture covers part of the one needed for particle combustion [7], its high
187 level impacts the HHV of biomass. The HHV of biomass is lower than
188 those of other fuels. However, the resulting char after the pyrolysis
189 phase tends to be more reactive than the char obtained during the
190 combustion of coal [39]. In addition, the alkalis in the biomass also
191 have a catalytic effect on the production of the char remaining after
192 pyrolysis [40, 41, 43].
- 193 - Biomass has a higher moisture content than other solid fuels. This
194 excess moisture delays the pyrolysis and ignition of volatiles because
195 of the energy required to dry the particle. Moreover, excess moisture
196 dilutes the content of alkali compounds in the biomass, inhibiting its
197 catalytic effects. Nevertheless, the reduction in alkali content reduces
198 the problems related to deposit formation on the surfaces of the furnace
199 [22]. Potassium and sodium, for example, are in the form of ions bound
200 to the organic matrix or as precipitated salts [42, 43]. Alkali compounds
201 are released during the reaction in two stages that coincide with the
202 pyrolysis and char combustion phases [43]. These minerals are soluble
203 in water and other solutions such as HCl that partially "wash down"
204 them from the biomass particle.

205 Because coal has a lower volatile content than biomass does, its combus-
206 tion may or may not present a pyrolysis stage followed by the oxidation-
207 gasification of the char. All this depends on the range of coal [6, 45]. How-
208 ever, given the low O/C molar ratio of coal, its calorific value is greater than

Figure 2: Fluid–dynamics states of the particles system. Based on Hobbs et al. [46]

209 biomass. Another typical characteristic of coal combustion is its lower re-
 210 activity, so its ignition starts at higher temperatures than that of biomass.
 211 In addition, the volatile flame presents intense luminosity due to the high
 212 formation of soot and tar [21].

213 3. Solid fuel combustion systems

214 The behaviour of solid fuel and its evolution throughout the sequential
 215 stages of combustion depend on the geometry and physicochemical properties
 216 of the particle. These properties lead to technical challenges when selecting a
 217 more suitable combustion technology for a given solid fuel. The contemplated
 218 approaches differ for each considered fuel [47].

219 Diverse burning techniques exist for solid fuels that work under a respec-
 220 tive fluid-dynamic regime of fuel particles. Hence, the technologies for solid

221 fuel combustion are classified into fixed-bed, fluidized-bed, and entrained bed
222 technologies (see Figure 2).

223 In a fixed-bed reactor, the superficial gas velocity that crosses the bed in
224 an upwards direction is insufficient to generate relative movement between
225 solid particles. If the gas velocity increases over the minimal fluidization
226 velocity, the fuel particles enter a state of partial suspension that enables
227 every particle to move randomly in the bed. Fluidized bed systems operate
228 under these conditions. Likewise, the fluidization state is divided into regimes
229 that depend on the intensity of the gas flow, from bubbling fluidization to
230 circulating fluidization. At high gas flows, which exceed the terminal velocity
231 of all the particles in the bed, the particles reach the state of pneumatic
232 transport (suspension). In this regime, each particle is dragged by the gas
233 or remains suspended inside the reactor.

234 *3.1. Solid fuel combustion in suspension systems*

235 Suspension combustion is the technology of most applications in large-
236 capacity thermoelectric plants, mainly to burn coal [6]. The extensive use of
237 coal is due to its high friability, allowing it to be pulverized to the dust scale.
238 The performance of a combustor of particles in suspension is comparable to
239 those of gas and liquid fuel burners [6]. However, suspension combustion
240 equipment has little flexibility with fuels other than those for which they
241 are designed, negatively impacting its efficiency [6, 48]. This is the case for
242 biomass, which possesses lower friability, a fibrous structure, and a high mois-
243 ture content that hinder the pulverization of its particles [22, 23]. Although
244 pretreatment techniques such as torrefaction improve biomass properties, en-
245 abling their combustion in suspension, this technology is dominant for coal

246 harnessing.

247 *3.2. Fluidized bed burners*

248 While not the focus of this review, fluidized bed burners constitute a
249 dominant space in thermoelectric plants, producing 20 MW_{th} or more [7].
250 This technology even challenges pulverized fuel equipment [5], especially in
251 applications involving coal [4]. Its prevalence is due to the inert material's
252 thermal and chemical properties, which account for 90–98% of the bed mass
253 [7]; the remainder comprises fuel particles. The level of agitation achieved
254 during the fluidization state and the heat capacity of the bed material allow
255 for high heat and mass transfer rates. Therefore, the temperature of the
256 bed may be constant. Additionally, the fluid–dynamic regime gives the bed
257 greater flexibility for working with particle sizes larger than those used in
258 suspension burners. This advantage depends on the capacity of the fuel
259 particles to attain a fluidized state with bed material. However, the inert
260 material is vulnerable to interactions with ashes that may lead to the sintering
261 of the bed. This problem affects the reactor's operation; as a result, the bed
262 temperature must be kept low (between 650–900 °C) [7]. Therefore, the use
263 of biofuels for combustion is restricted to biomass with a low alkali content.

264 *3.3. Fixed-bed combustion technology*

265 Fixed-bed combustion is the oldest and most common conversion method
266 for the energy use of solid fuels [5, 46]. In these systems, particles stacked on
267 the grate form a porous medium through which the combustion air flows, pro-
268 moting thermochemical reactions in the solid phase. The fuel gases released
269 during the pyrolysis and gasification stages and the entrained fine particles

270 burn in suspension through secondary air injection. There are different clas-
271 sifications for fixed-bed burners: (1) the manner in which the fuel particles
272 feed the reactor – underfeed, overfeed, and spread-stokers; (2) the mecha-
273 nism used to move the bed inside the burner – traveling, moving, vibrating,
274 and chain-grate; and (3) the direction in which the flame front propagates
275 relative to the airflow direction – cocurrent and countercurrent (Figure 3).
276 However, the latter classification is usually employed in terms of the physics
277 phenomena presented during bed combustion. As shown in Figure 3, coun-
278 tercurrent systems have an ignition front that advances towards the air inlet,
279 with fresh fuel closer to this inlet, whereas cocurrent devices have an ignition
280 front that advances away from the air inlet.

281 The reaction zone is the region inside the bed where the fuel particles enter
282 the combustion stage. The reaction zone is very narrow in a countercurrent
283 setup because the flame front and oxidant stream flow in opposite directions.
284 Fresh fuel is heated mainly by radiation, as the air flow and the ignition wave
285 advance in opposite directions, preventing other forms of heat transport from
286 being effective [49]. Consequently, the flame front propagates slowly along
287 the bed. In contrast, in a cocurrent setup, as the oxidant flow and flame
288 front move in the same direction, radiation and convection contribute to the
289 combustion heat reaching a broader region of unreacted particles. Therefore,
290 the reaction zone is thicker in the cocurrent regime and propagates faster than
291 in the countercurrent mechanism. Despite their disadvantage compared with
292 the cocurrent setup, the countercurrent mechanism is extensively used in
293 grate-combustion installations. Conversely, cocurrent air flow and reaction
294 front systems are more common in gasification processes.

Figure 3: Fixed bed combustion setups in function of the relative direction between the flame front propagation and oxidant flow. (a) countercurrent, (b) cocurrent

295 Fixed-bed reactors are highly flexible in that they are suitable for the
 296 combustion of feedstock that would be deemed inappropriate for other tech-
 297 nologies owing to their particle size or chemistry. For this reason, they are
 298 widely used in biomass cogeneration plants and municipal solid waste incin-
 299 eration [5, 50] to reduce the large volume of waste generated and, at the
 300 same time, produce thermal energy [39, 51, 52]. Additionally, residential
 301 and domestic appliances extensively use this technology to burn biomass,
 302 such as wood logs, for heating purposes [53, 54]. However, many medium-
 303 and large-sized fixed-bed combustion apparatuses for burning biofuels must
 304 be updated. The design of these plants was initially derived from combus-
 305 tors for burning coal [39]. Therefore, the use of biomass requires adapta-
 306 tions to ensure regular equipment performance during operation. Although
 307 some problems remain during the operation of fixed-bed burners, such as
 308 unburned carbon losses, particulate matter emissions, and combustion insta-
 309 bilities, these installations manage to fulfill their primary functions. These

310 problems are associated with knowing the most appropriate operating con-
311 ditions to burn the growing biomass supply with energy potential [55, 56].

312 The following sections present the principal results of works related to
313 biomass particle combustion in fixed-bed reactors.

314 **4. Description of laboratory-scale fixed-bed reactors**

315 Establishing operating criteria for the efficient performance of combus-
316 tion devices requires knowledge of the transformations that fuel undergoes
317 during combustion. Ideally, such transformations should be monitored un-
318 der the burner’s operating conditions. However, this task demands technical
319 and economic challenges because of the equipment’s structural configuration
320 [57–59]. There are limitations to accessing industrial burners with measure-
321 ment instruments, especially in grate combustion systems, where the main
322 combustion reactions occur within the bed [57, 58, 60]. In contrast, experi-
323 mental setups involve simplistic geometries and total control over operative
324 parameters, allowing the continuous monitoring of a fuel sample during its
325 combustion. These setups facilitate an understanding of the basic physical
326 phenomena behind the macroscopic behaviour around solid fuel combustion.

327 Among the different experimental techniques used to study solid fuel com-
328 bustion, laboratory-scale fixed-bed reactors stand out because the conditions
329 emulated during their operation are very close to those observed in industrial
330 equipment [15, 61, 62]. These systems are robust tools for observing bed be-
331 haviour as a function of controlled variations in operational parameters [63].
332 Figure 4 shows a schematic representation of a laboratory-scale fixed-bed
333 reactor setup and the basic systems that compose it. These systems include

334 the following:

Figure 4: Generic laboratory-scale fixed-bed reactor setup. The symbols T , m , and χ , represent the measured signals of the bed temperature, bed mass, and flue gas composition, respectively.

335 **Combustion chamber** The combustion chamber consists of a circular or
336 rectangular container inside which the sample is placed. These vessels
337 have internal diameters between 150 mm and 250 mm, with heights
338 ranging from 800 mm to 1500 mm. At the bottom of the chamber,
339 the sample rests on a grate through which the oxidant gas enters. Al-
340 though bricks were initially used to build the combustion chambers
341 [64], in general, stainless steel is the material employed because of its
342 high temperatures and corrosion strength [52, 65–71]. However, the
343 combustion chamber is usually thermally isolated to increase the repli-
344 cability of the results and enable their comparison with other methods.
345 Along the combustion chamber, some orifices are used for measurement

346 and gas sampling. Some works have adapted a section for direct ob-
347 servation of the evolution of a sample, using glass with high thermal
348 resistance [72–75]. Furthermore, some installations include additional
349 systems on the freeboard to study some processes present in industrial
350 burners, such as heat exchangers [76] or heat deflectors [74].

351 **Combustion air supply system** A fan is typically the main component
352 of a combustion air supply system. This fan sends the air from the
353 atmosphere to the plenum under the grate through a duct. The grate
354 distributes the air entering the combustion chamber through its ori-
355 fices and supports the fuel bed. Generally, the porosity of the grate
356 coincides with those employed in industrial furnaces [77]. The fan’s
357 motor rotation speed is controlled to obtain the desired air flux. Some
358 setups incorporate air staging [78], exhaust gas recirculation [79] or a
359 continuous fuel-feeding system. Other systems add electric heaters to
360 study the effect of air preheating over the combustion bed.

361 **Measurement and acquisition system** Because of the large samples used
362 in experiments, it is possible to measure local properties inside the bed
363 during its combustion continuously. The properties monitored during
364 each experiment include:

365 - **Bed temperature variation:** Thermocouples inserted into the
366 bed through orifices along the combustion chamber measure the
367 temperature variation. In the region where the combustion cham-
368 ber is filled with bed particles, the radiative effect on temperature
369 is difficult to assess, because the particles in the bed surround each

370 inserted thermocouple and may be in direct contact with the ther-
371 mocouple. Radiation can affect the absolute value measured, but
372 the conditions are similar for all thermocouples, and the differ-
373 ential behaviour between thermocouples is maintained. However,
374 this simplification is inconsistent in the combustion chamber over
375 the bed, the freeboard [80].

376 - **Flue gas composition:** Different instruments have been used
377 to measure the flue gas concentration both continuously and non-
378 continuously. Such measurements are made through in situ gas
379 sampling, as the presence of solid fuel prevents the application of
380 optical sensors to identify species and radicals, as is usually done
381 in gas phase combustion. However, solid matter in condensed
382 phases (tar, particulate material) and high temperatures generate
383 extreme conditions for *in situ* measurements. Therefore, most ex-
384 perimental setups integrate a flue gas conditioner system before
385 gas injection into the composition detector instrument. This so-
386 lution has limited the understanding of evolution of the gaseous
387 species from their liberation from fuel particles.

388 - **Mass variation:** Electronic balances are used to record the mass
389 variation of the fuel bed over time. This setup can be configured
390 either with the reactor suspended or placed on top of the balance
391 to ensure precise mass measurements throughout the combustion
392 process.

393 Despite the simplicity of these setups, researchers and engineers have
394 drawn operation criteria from experimental results over the most critical

395 parameters in fixed-bed combustion – airflow rate, fuel feeding rate, and
396 ignition time. Furthermore, the results obtained offer data to validate nu-
397 merical models. Nevertheless, some discrepancies arise because the samples
398 consist of a batch of particles. In an experimental setup, each fuel particle
399 conserves its position relative to the other during the test. However, some
400 grate types induce movements on the bed to improve combustion in industrial
401 burners. The absence of movement in a sample is the primary error source
402 when experimental results are applied to industrial burners with grates that
403 induce particle movement [61, 62, 81, 82]. Even so, the data obtained are
404 very accurate for travelling grate burners [61, 83, 84].

405 In addition to the above discrepancies, fuel particles are ideally packed in
406 a laboratory-scale fixed-bed reactor with a uniform size distribution. Oth-
407 erwise, the odd of high porosity spots inside the bed may induce bed chan-
408 nelling [85]. Channelling is caused by interconnected void spaces in the ma-
409 trix formed by the packed bed, generating preferential passages for the air
410 or gas flow to traverse. These preferential routes cause the ignition front to
411 propagate much faster along the inner surfaces of the passage than over other
412 surfaces of the bed, causing chaotic burning patterns and significant fluctua-
413 tions and peaks in temperature [85–88]. In the last section of this review, we
414 discuss channelling. In the following paragraphs, we describe the combustion
415 process of an ideally packed bed as observed during an experimental test.

416 **5. Fuel particle fixed-bed combustion**

417 Figure 5 illustrates a laboratory-scale reactor’s fixed-bed combustion pro-
418 cess with a batch countercurrent configuration. Following ignition on the bed

Figure 5: Description of the combustion process in an experimental fixed-bed.

419 surface, an ignition front forms and propagates downwards across the bed in
 420 the opposite direction of the air stream (Figure 5-a). This wave is flat and
 421 normal to its path because of the uniform temperature distribution along
 422 the cross-section [58, 64, 89, 90]. When the ignition front reaches unreacted
 423 fuel particles, their temperature suddenly increases, causing such particles
 424 to undergo drying and pyrolysis phases (Figure 5-b). Pyrolysis gases enter
 425 combustion, consuming oxygen from the air flow. Char particles compose the
 426 layers left behind by the ignition front, exposing them to oxygen, combus-
 427 tion gases, and volatiles. In this environment, combustion and gasification
 428 reactions deplete char particles [91–93], and consequently the bed volume
 429 progressively shrinks. When the ignition front reaches the region near the
 430 grate, almost all the volatile content in the fuel particles runs out (Figure 5-
 431 c). Therefore, the oxygen in the air is available to react with residual char
 432 particle layers, and a new reaction front forms. This new front travels cocur-
 433 rent with the airflow, leaving ashes in its way (Figure 5-d).

434 The ignition front establishes a thermochemical boundary between fresh
435 particles and those that have started the combustion process by entering the
436 drying phase. This region is defined as the reaction zone. Therefore, the
437 ignition front serves as a reaction zone mobile border.

438 Three graphs obtained from measurements during the experiment de-
439 scribe the combustion behaviour of a fuel bed sample: temperature history,
440 mass variation, and flue gas composition. Despite the stochastic nature of
441 these profiles, their tendencies are conserved independent of the fuel tested
442 [61, 94]. Indeed, Lenis et al. [63] evaluated the repeatability of fixed-bed com-
443 bustion experiments in a laboratory-scale burner. By analysis of variance,
444 they determined, with 95% reliability, that the fixed-bed combustion param-
445 eters – ignition front propagation velocity, burning rate, and stoichiometric
446 ratio – are repeatable.

447 Below, we describe each of these three characteristic plots. Figures 6 to 8
448 show the results obtained from eucalyptus residue combustion experiments
449 in a laboratory-scale fixed-bed reactor [77].

450 *5.1. History of bed temperature*

451 The ignition front generally arises on the fuel bed top and travels down-
452 wards to the grate. The thermocouples at different heights along the bed
453 record the temperature variation at a fixed location as the ignition front
454 moves. This graph is defined as a history of the bed temperature or temper-
455 ature history. Figure 6 shows the history of bed temperature from sugarcane
456 bagasse experimental data measured in a laboratory-scale reactor [77]. Ad-
457 ditionally, Figure 6 presents the isothermal field in function of time and
458 position. In the graph, four regions, defined as (a), (b), (c), and (d) divide

Figure 6: History of the bed temperature profile and isothermal field as a function of the thermocouples position and time [77]

459 the curves with vertical lines. These indices correspond with those shown in
460 Figure 5 and indicate four states of local combustion temperature at 180 mm
461 above the grate.

462 When the particles in a bed layer enter the reaction zone, their temper-
463 ature increases abruptly from room temperature (state (a)). Rapidly, the
464 particles go through drying and pyrolysis phases. The volatiles released from
465 fuel particles reach their flammability point and ignite, increasing the local
466 temperature (state (b)). During this period, the particles under combustion
467 reactions surround the thermocouple. The isothermal lines in this phase have
468 a constant slope in the diagram of height vs. time, which indicates that the
469 ignition front propagates through the bed at constant velocity (Figure 6).
470 The local temperature reaches a peak value when the bed surface reaches
471 the thermocouple. From this moment on, the thermocouple is exposed to
472 the reactor walls, which, along with the oxidant current, dissipate part of the
473 heat released from the combustion of char particles and volatiles [13, 65, 95–
474 97]. Additionally, some char particles in contact with the thermocouple un-
475 dergo gasification reactions which also contribute to local temperature re-
476 duction. Because of the heat dissipation effect, which is also a consequence
477 of the gasification reactions of char particles in contact with CO_2 and steam
478 [12, 66, 91, 98], the local temperature decreases. However, the reactions
479 of fuel particles in the middle of the ignition front path reduce the degree
480 of local temperature variation (state (c)). When the ignition front reaches
481 the grate, the thermocouple reads another temperature increase. This ef-
482 fect results from the high oxygen availability, which consumes residual char
483 particles left after all volatile material is depleted [66, 99, 100]. The tem-

484 perature decreases when the combustible material present in the bed is not
 485 sufficient to sustain a high temperature (state (d)). At this point, dissipative
 486 effects prevail, cooling the reactor. As shown in the height vs. time plot
 487 (Figure 6), the isothermal lines in this last phase are almost vertical because
 488 the temperature is the same at all positions of the combustion chamber.

489 From the temperature history, it is possible to estimate the ignition front
 490 propagation velocity as follows:

- 491 1. For each thermocouple inserted along the combustion chamber, it is
 492 necessary to define any reference temperature (T_{ref}) during the ignition
 493 phase (as (b) in Figure 6). There are two approaches for selecting
 494 T_{ref} : (i) by choosing any temperature inside the ignition phase and
 495 (ii) by estimating the temperature inflection point (in Figure 6 this
 496 temperature is defined as "inf."), which is present at the sharp change
 497 in the temperature profile from room conditions.
- 498 2. To calculate the ratio of the distance between adjacent thermocouples
 499 ($H_{i+1} - H_i$) and the time when each thermocouple registers T_{ref} is
 500 measured ($t(T_{ref})_{i+1} - t(T_{ref})_i$).
- 501 3. Finally, the ignition front velocity is obtained by the average of the
 502 ratios estimated in the previous step.

$$v_{ig} = \frac{1}{N_T - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_T-1} \frac{H_{i+1} - H_i}{t(T_{ref})_{i+1} - t(T_{ref})_i} \quad (1)$$

503 The ignition front velocity varies along each bed section [98] because
 504 nonuniform bed porosity affects airflow distribution [63]. However, by taking
 505 the slope of the regression line formed by isothermal points in a position vs.

506 time diagram, as shown in Figure 6, it is possible to reduce the deviation in
507 v_{ig} .

508 An additional approach for v_{ig} estimation uses visual techniques [75, 101].
509 Polesek-Karczewska et al. [75] used a camera to take pictures of the combus-
510 tion process of poultry residues on a fixed-bed reactor. Then, the authors
511 decomposed each photograph pixel colour in its RGB constituents with im-
512 age processing software. After that, they found the position of the ignition
513 front in the bed because, during combustion, there is an intensity peak re-
514 lated to the red colour inside the reaction zone. With the position of the
515 ignition front during bed combustion, it was possible to estimate v_{ig} . The
516 velocities obtained using this method and those estimated from thermocouple
517 measurements converged [75].

518 With the v_{ig} ignition rate, \dot{m}''_{ig} , is determined. The ignition rate defines
519 the mass swept by the ignition front during its propagation along the bed,
520 per unit of time and surface [86]. \dot{m}''_{ig} is directly related to the bed's release
521 rate of volatile gases, also called the pyrolysis rate [49]. The ignition rate
522 is the result of the product between the ignition front propagation velocity
523 (v_{ig}) and raw bed bulk density (ρ_b).

$$\dot{m}''_{ig} = \rho_b v_{ig} \quad (2)$$

524 5.2. Bed mass variation

525 Figure 7 shows a typical mass variation profile during a combustion test.
526 After bed ignition, there is a period in which the bed mass loss rate (slope
527 of bed mass variation profile versus time) progressively increases as the re-
528 actions associated with combustion reach their stable state [98, 102, 103].

Figure 7: Bed mass variation over time. The letters (a), (b), (c), and (d) represent the moments in Figure 5 [77].

529 After transitory effects, the bed mass linearly decreases, indicating that the
 530 reaction zone moves at an average constant velocity. The experimental con-
 531 ditions are established from this moment, and the relevant measurements
 532 may be taken. Finally, when almost all combustible material runs out, the
 533 slope of the curve slowly decreases as the combustion extinguishes.

534 The burning rate, \dot{m}''_{bur} , is a parameter that represents the mass flux
 535 released as a result of fuel combustion-gasification reactions. It measures the
 536 instant mass deficit along the bed. Therefore, \dot{m}''_{bur} includes the loss of mass
 537 caused by moisture vaporization, volatile release, char consumption, and fine
 538 particle entrainment. The burning rate is estimated by Equation 3:

$$\dot{m}''_{bur} = \frac{1}{A_{bed}} \frac{dm}{dt} \quad (3)$$

539 where m is the mass of the bed at instant t , taken when the reaction zone
 540 propagates stably (Figure 7), A_{bed} is the cross-section of the fixed-bed and

541 $\frac{dm}{dt}$ the sample mass loss rate.

542 5.3. Flue gas composition

543 The data plotted in Figure 8 correspond to measurements of the flue gas
544 composition taken over the bed in a laboratory-scale bed combustion reactor
545 [104]. Although the composition of flue gases is acquired above the freeboard,
546 away from the reaction zone, the temporal composition profiles obtained are
547 similar to those obtained at a position within the bed, as observed in various
548 studies in the literature [60, 105, 106]. However, this similarity is consistent
549 from the moment the reaction zone progresses steadily towards the grate.

550 After bed ignition (or when the ignition front passes the gas sampling
551 port), the O_2 level is very low. In contrast, CO and CO_2 concentrations
552 increase to reach a peak. These transitory events indicate that the fuel
553 layers enter in combustion. During the stable stage of bed combustion, the
554 CO and CO_2 levels remain relatively uniform until the ignition front reaches
555 the grate at the end of the steady phase. At this time, at approximately 375
556 s, as shown in Figure 8, the CO concentration increases, and CO_2 decreases
557 because of char gasification reactions [55, 107]:

558 When volatile gases are completely depleted from residual fuel particles, the
559 O_2 availability for char combustion increases. Consequently, CO level de-
560 creases to zero, and the CO_2 concentration increases until reaches a last
561 maximum before it decreases to zero as residual combustible material burns.

Figure 8: Evolution of the flue gas level during experimental tests of a sugarcane bagasse fixed-bed [104]

562 In the case of the NO_x level, represented by the NO variation in Figure 8,
 563 its graph has three representative features:

- 564 1. A few seconds after bed ignition, the NO content increases rapidly. For
 565 example, NO_x precursors, HCN and NH_3 , are produced by volatiliza-
 566 tion and oxidized to form NO. When the O_2 content decreases as the
 567 oxidation of volatiles consumes it, NO acts as an oxidant according
 568 to the reactions [108–110] although the pathways can be much more
 569 complex than this set of reactions [111]:

570 NO formation stops, and its concentration decreases. This behaviour
571 can be observed in Figure 8.

- 572 2. After the sampling orifice is immersed inside the reaction zone, the NO
573 level subsequently stabilizes, as do the HCN and NH_3 concentrations,
574 as several authors showed [105, 112, 113].
- 575 3. When the ignition front arrives at the grate, the reduction in volatiles
576 causes O_2 availability to increase for char oxidation. This event pro-
577 motes NO production, and its concentration reaches a maximum [112,
578 113], as shown in Figure 8. Finally, NO formation stops along with the
579 reactive-to-oxygen compounds in char.

580 The variation in fixed-bed combustion stoichiometry with airflow rate also
581 affects NO_x formation and destruction rates. Increasing the ignition rate with
582 higher airflow rate increases the amount of volatile material released in the
583 reaction zone. Consequently, the level of NO_x precursor gases emitted from
584 biomass, as NH_3 , HCN, and NO, increases [114]. Because bed combustion
585 in the initial stages is carried out under rich conditions, some combustible
586 gases, such as CO, use NO as an oxidant according to reactions 3 to 7, as

587 shown in Figure 9. However, further increases in the airflow rate intensify
 588 the amount of O₂ available to produce higher amounts of NO_x, mainly NO
 589 [65, 96, 115], by the side reaction 8, which is more important in temperature
 590 above 950 °C:

591 Techniques for reducing emissions "in situ" have been studied in fixed-
 592 bed experimental systems that can be applied at an industrial scale. Archan
 593 et al. [79] investigated the effects of using flue gas recirculation on the spatial
 594 distribution of gaseous species in an experimental combustor, and Polonini
 595 et al. [116] also experimentally tested flue gas recirculation, which resulted
 596 in reductions in CO, particulate matter and NOx emissions. Some of these
 597 trends were confirmed by CFD simulations by Gómez et al. [117]. However,
 598 the phenomena that occur inside the bed still need to be further investigated,
 599 as in these studies the effects and mechanisms also include the action of
 600 secondary air.

601 The mean concentration value of any gas species $[X]$ is obtained by cal-
 602 culating the area under its temporal variation graph (Figure 8) over the total
 603 experimental time:

$$[X] = \frac{1}{t_{tot}} \int_0^{t_{tot}} [x] dt \quad (4)$$

604 where $[x]$ is the concentration of the specie at the time t , and t_{tot} is the total
 605 time of data acquisition.

606 The flue gas composition allows us to determine which reactions must be
 607 intensified to reduce nonburned fuel gases or the emission of pollutants [97].

Figure 9: Variation in total NO production with bed stoichiometry: ■ straw (left axis) [114], and △ forestry residues (right axis) [65]

608 The properties defined above – the ignition rate, burning rate, and mean
 609 concentration of species $[X]$ – describe the behaviour of the reaction zone dur-
 610 ing its displacement along the bed and characterize the reactor performance.
 611 However, other essential characteristics allow more profound insight into the
 612 fixed-bed combustion phenomenon to set reference conditions for evaluating
 613 numerical models. Figure 10 shows some of these parameters together with
 614 those previously discussed. These properties are defined as the reaction zone
 615 thickness, δ , maximum bed temperature, T_{max} , particulate matter emission
 616 rate, particle size, and bed packing characteristics.

617 *Reaction zone thickness (δ).* The reaction zone is where reactions that sup-
 618 port ignition front propagation along the bed occur [95, 118]. The ignition
 619 front and the cross-section with nonreacting particles, close to the bed’s top,
 620 limit the reaction zone (Figure 10). Therefore, inside this region the sto-
 621 ichiometry of fixed-bed combustion is determined by estimating the ratio

Figure 10: Main parameters in fixed-bed combustion.

622 between air flowrate and ignition rate:

$$[A/F] = \frac{\dot{m}''_{air}}{\dot{m}''_{ig}} \quad (5)$$

623 where $[A/F]$ represents the air-to-fuel ratio inside the reaction zone. This
 624 region results from the difference between the ignition rate and burning rate
 625 [87, 119] since bed ignition.

626 Initially, fuel particles absorb heat from an ignition source. Depending
 627 on factors such as the heat flow intensity from the ignition source, bulk
 628 density, and airflow rate, the heat transferred reaches a certain depth inside
 629 the bed. Those particles directly exposed to the ignition source increase their
 630 temperature and go through drying and pyrolysis stages. In some locations in
 631 the ignition source influence zone, the mixture of combustible gases with air
 632 reaches its lower flammability limit, and combustion begins. Additionally,
 633 the formed char starts to burn. The heat released during combustion is
 634 transferred, by radiation and conduction, downwards to fresh fuel particles
 635 out of the ignition source influence zone [81]. The ignition front forms and
 636 propagates hereafter, as explained in the above sections. Because the char

637 consumption rate is lower than the ignition rate, those particles left behind
638 from the ignition front continue the combustion process, and a reaction zone
639 is established. The reaction zone thickness depends mainly on the oxidant
640 flow rate and reaction kinetics.

641 Because the volume of fuel particles only shrinks during the char con-
642 sumption phase, it is possible to directly relate the bed top surface dis-
643 placement velocity with the char consumption rate. Therefore, from the
644 evolution of the reaction zone thickness, strategies to improve airflow dis-
645 tribution across the grate and reduce unburned-particle-related combustion
646 inefficiencies are possible [102].

647 There are challenges associated with measuring δ caused by difficulties in
648 following the bed top surface position without affecting the combustion pro-
649 cess. Nevertheless, some authors have successfully estimated this position
650 experimentally [83, 97, 102, 103]. Stubington and Fenton [83] employed a
651 graduated rod to directly measure the bed top surface position during fixed-
652 bed combustion experiments of sugarcane residues. Porteiro et al. [102] used
653 an articulated auxiliary structure to monitor the bed height during experi-
654 ments with wood pellet samples. Junejo et al. [103] measured the bed level
655 position with a hollow steel bar used as a height indicator. Yang et al. [97]
656 estimated δ from the temperature history profile and ignition front velocity.
657 They defined δ as the physical distance in the bed from the room to the peak
658 temperature.

659 *Maximum bed temperature.* The literature reports that the maximum com-
660 bustion temperatures are lower than 1300 °C. However, some biomass com-
661 bustion effects carried out at temperatures below this value are of techni-

662 cal and environmental interest. For instance, ashes produced during some
663 biomass combustion have low melting temperatures because of the elevated
664 presence of alkali compounds and chlorine. These compounds partially melt
665 or even vaporize at low temperatures – approximately 873 K [51]– dur-
666 ing combustion and react on burner and boiler surfaces to form deposits.
667 The occurrence of ash-related problems can be controlled based on previous
668 knowledge of the composition of the inorganic compounds in the fuel and
669 the maximum temperature reached during combustion [120]. Because the
670 maximum combustion temperature is associated with the combustion heat
671 released, it is also used as a burner performance indicator.

672 *Particulate matter.* One disadvantage of using fixed-bed burners is the high
673 emission of fine particles released from the fuel bed. The particles released
674 during solid fuel combustion are made of ashes, soot, and char. The impacts
675 that particulate matter has on the integrity of equipment, health, and the
676 environment are highly discussed in the literature [51]. Like estimating the
677 reaction zone thickness, diverse methodologies are used to quantify the par-
678 ticulate matter emitted during a fixed-bed combustion test. Nevertheless,
679 the potential impact of a fuel bed on the release of particulate matter is re-
680 lated to the emission rate. This parameter represents the mass of particles
681 emitted in flue gases over either the initial mass of fuel or the net energy
682 liberated during the test [69].

683 Few experimental studies have aimed to research the formation of particu-
684 late emissions during biomass combustion in fixed-bed burners. Among these
685 works, the contributions of Wiinikka and collaborators stand out [67, 121–
686 123]. They investigated the evolution of the particulate matter released dur-

687 ing the combustion of different wood samples in an experimental fixed-bed
688 reactor with a staged air supply. They discovered the critical role of fuel
689 composition and the burner's operational conditions in forming the fine par-
690 ticle mode – with a size smaller than $2.5 \mu\text{m}$. Unlike entrained particles, fine
691 particles are of primary concern because their small size prevents their sepa-
692 ration from flue gases by conventional systems [67]. Their formation depends
693 on the fuel used in the bed, as noted by Mantananont and Patumsawad [69]
694 and Sommersacher et al. [124]. Reducing the char temperature at bed level
695 and increasing the mixture rate in the secondary oxidation zone reduced the
696 quantity of particulate matter present during wood samples combustion test
697 [67, 113]. However, in fixed-bed combustion tests of wood carried out by Pet-
698 tersson et al. [125] in an experimental reactor without a staged air supply,
699 the particulate matter emissions were unaffected by bed temperature.

700 *Particle size and bed packing characteristics.* The phenomena associated with
701 the combustion of a solid particle are surface phenomena. The size, shape,
702 and density of a fuel particle affect its consumption time. However, packing
703 properties – size distribution, bulk density, and porosity – also influence the
704 combustion of a fixed-bed of particles. Because the individual and group
705 physical characteristics of the particles are closely related, it is impossible
706 to study the effect of one parameter separately without affecting the others
707 [126]. Additionally, because fuel particles are nonuniform in shape and size,
708 it is necessary to describe the bed particle population by a particle size
709 distribution and an estimator of that distribution [127].

710 At the individual particle level, its size depends on the shape of the parti-
711 cle. Therefore, a characteristic dimension is defined. For example, the length

712 depicts slender and cylindrical particles; in the case of flattened particles, a
713 particle diameter (d_p) is usually the best choice. Different definitions of d_p
714 include hydraulic diameter, surface diameter, sieve diameter, and surface-
715 volume diameter or Sauter diameter (d_{sv}). Hallett et al. [128] simulated
716 fixed-bed combustion of commercial hardwood charcoal using different par-
717 ticle diameter definitions to describe the bed. Compared with experimental
718 data, the numerical results revealed that d_{sv} is the most suitable parameter
719 for representing the particle diameter in models of processes that include
720 surface chemical reactions.

721 The following equation is used to calculate the Sauter diameter:

$$d_{sv} = \frac{d_v^3}{d_s^2} \quad (6)$$

722 where, d_v is the particle volume diameter – the diameter of a sphere with a
723 similar volume to the particle – and d_s is the surface diameter – the diameter
724 of a sphere with the same surface area as the particle.

725 At the bed scale, the nature of the phenomena carried out between solid
726 particles and the surrounding gases are related to porosity (ϕ). ϕ is the ratio
727 between the volume of the voids in the bed and the total bed volume and is
728 expressed in terms of the particle density (ρ_p) and bulk density (ρ_b):

$$\phi = 1 - \frac{\rho_b}{\rho_p} \quad (7)$$

729 In the next section, we discuss the effects of varying the dominant oper-
730 ating parameters on fixed-bed combustion.

731 **6. Effect of the most influential operational factors on fixed-bed**
732 **combustion**

733 *6.1. Effect of oxidant medium*

734 The mass flow rate of an oxidant medium – such as air (\dot{m}_a'') – is the
735 most influential parameter during bed combustion. In conjunction with the
736 ignition front, the oxidant medium controls the stoichiometry inside the re-
737 action zone. Its variation impacts the stability and propagation of the bed’s
738 reaction zone and the formation of pollutant compounds (for instance, NO_x).
739 These effects on bed combustion behaviour depend on the composition of the
740 oxidant medium and the dynamics of its flow through the bed. For a given
741 oxidant medium, oxygen availability affects the energy released during the
742 combustion of volatile material and char particles. The mass flux of the oxi-
743 dant controls this availability. However, this parameter induces a convective
744 effect that dissipates the heat from combustion. Thus, reaction front prop-
745 agation results from the net heat transferred to every fuel particle in layers
746 near the reaction zone.

747 Various studies have reported the influence of the thermodynamic state
748 (temperature and composition) and the oxidant medium’s flow dynamics
749 (superficial velocity) over fixed-bed combustion. Their results show that the
750 reaction zone may present different behaviours depending on the combination
751 of these parameters. The following sections expose the most discussed effects
752 of the oxidant medium on fixed-bed combustion:

- 753 1. We present the effect of the mass flux of the oxidant for a given com-
754 position and temperature, specifically, air.
- 755 2. The effects of the oxidant medium temperature are noted.

Figure 11: Variation in the ignition rate with the air flux. The dashed line represents stoichiometric conditions. Based on Shin and Choi [118].

756 3. The influence of the oxidant medium composition is discussed.

757 6.1.1. Combustion regimes

758 Regardless of the fuel used in the bed, the ignition and burning rates show
 759 similar trends with variations in the oxidant flux rate. Figure 11 illustrates
 760 this behaviour. Additionally, this behaviour has been observed in oxidizing
 761 media other than air, such as mixtures of CO_2 with O_2 [92] and mixtures of
 762 N_2 with different concentrations of O_2 [129]. The similarity observed in each
 763 fuel allows for the identification that the combustion process takes place in
 764 different regimes depending on the magnitude of the oxidant medium flow
 765 rate supplied. These regimes also set boundaries inside which bed reactions
 766 occur. Each of these regimes and their main characteristics are discussed
 767 below.

768 *Oxygen-limited regime.* The first regime arises for very low air flux, but with
 769 enough oxygen available to sustain a flammable mixture with volatile gases

770 [49, 95]. Under these conditions, the volatiles released stay close to the fuel
771 particles and maintain a cloud around them. The gases start combustion in
772 those particle bed layers near the ignition front. The slow reaction kinetics
773 and insufficient mixture of pyrolysis gases and oxygen induce combustion un-
774 der very rich conditions [130]; therefore, a significant portion of the volatiles
775 leave the bed without reacting [50, 96, 118]. The reactions concentrate the re-
776 leased heat near the ignition front, supporting its propagation along the bed
777 but under transitory conditions. Over the ignition front, a layer of unburned
778 particles builds up [83, 95], but only a fraction receives heat from the ignition
779 front. These particles react slowly, mainly by gasification [50, 96, 130]. Since
780 \dot{m}''_{bur} in this layer of particles is much lower than v_{ig} (Figure 12), the reaction
781 zone thickness continually increases until ignition front reaches the bottom
782 of the bed [83, 131]. Some authors define this transitory phase as gasification
783 with incomplete consumption of oxygen [49, 50, 118, 130]. Pérez et al. [132]
784 designate this combustion as a smouldering process because heterogeneous
785 reactions rule and sustain the combustion of the bed.

786 Increasing the airflow rate increases the oxygen availability and the reac-
787 tion and heat release rates [118, 133]; additionally, the combustion tempera-
788 ture, ignition rate, and burning increase. Hence, the growth of the reaction
789 zone thickness decreases. A new transition to another regime arises when
790 the reaction rate exceeds the oxygen supply rate. Under these conditions,
791 all the oxygen in the reaction zone is wholly consumed in the bed. This
792 transition was defined by Rönnbäck et al. [50] as gasification with complete
793 oxygen consumption.

794 The reaction rate increases with increasing oxygen availability in the two

795 transitions described above.

796 *Reaction-limited regime.* At a higher airflow rate, the oxygen availability
797 within the reaction zone and the convective dissipation rate of the air stream
798 increase [133]. Depending on the fuel properties and bed characteristics, two
799 situations can occur:

800 - The first case occurs when the reaction rate reaches a maximum before
801 the convective effect of the airflow is of the same magnitude. In this
802 situation, \dot{m}''_{ig} and \dot{m}''_{bur} are approximately similar; therefore, the reac-
803 tion zone stably travels along the bed holding its thickness (Figure 12)
804 [134]. This situation is characterized by the absence of the char burn-
805 ing stage after the ignition front reaches the bed bottom [135–137]. As
806 its velocity increases, the reaction zone narrows at higher airflow ve-
807 locities. However, the increase in \dot{m}''_{ig} and \dot{m}''_{bur} with the increment in
808 airflow rate is lower than that observed in the oxygen-limited regime.
809 This trend continues until the ignition and burning rates reach their
810 maximum values when the reaction zone thickness is minimized [138].
811 Figure 12 shows this behaviour.

812 - The second situation occurs when the convective dissipation rate at-
813 tains the reaction rate before the latter reaches its maximum. In this
814 case, despite \dot{m}''_{ig} and \dot{m}''_{bur} increase with airflow rate, the reaction zone
815 unstably propagates through the bed. Like in the first case, increasing
816 the reaction zone propagation rates requires an even higher airflow rate,
817 but as \dot{m}''_{ig} and \dot{m}''_{bur} are different, the reaction zone thickness continues
818 increasing and accumulating material before the ignition front reaches

Figure 12: Effects of airflow rate variation on the ignition and combustion rates for several types of biomass: straw [87], switchgrass [87], and cardboard [88]. \square Burning rate, \blacksquare Ignition rate.

819 the grate. Khor et al. [87] observed this behaviour during the com-
820 bustion of straw and switchgrass samples in an experimental fixed-bed
821 reactor (Figure 12).

822 In both situations described above, fixed-bed combustion is limited by
823 the maximum reaction rate and the convective dissipation rate [118]. Various
824 authors define this regime as limited by the reaction. This regime is present
825 until the ignition and burning rates reach their maximum values. Here, the
826 release of heat and convective dissipation rates are balanced [136].

827 *Extinction regime.* The critical air flux ($\dot{m}''_{a,cr}$) is a parameter defined as the
828 air flux rate at which the ignition and burning rates reach their maxima,
829 which limits fixed-bed combustion efficiency.

830 At airflow rates higher than $\dot{m}''_{a,cr}$, the intensity of heat release is lower
831 than the convective dissipation rate. Therefore, the airstream cools the char
832 particles and drags the volatile flame away from the bed [132]. At some
833 airflow rates, the temperature of the reaction zone is very low, and the com-
834 bustion extinguishes. Conversely, because the volatility of some elements
835 in the ashes decreases with decreasing temperature, the deposition on the
836 burner surfaces caused by inorganic vapour condensation diminishes [139].
837 This is known as the extinction regime [58, 61].

838 The combustion regime profile for a fixed-bed, as shown in Figure 12
839 depends on fuel properties, such as particle geometry, thermal degradation
840 kinetics, and bed characteristics. [49, 97, 126, 132, 141]. In Figure 12, it is
841 possible to point out that both the height – defined by the maximum ignition
842 rate – and the graph width are different from one fuel to another.

Figure 13: Effects of air flux on the ignition rate for some fixed-bed fuels: straw [87]; pine and wood pellets [58]; high-temperature coke [138]; and RDF [140]. The data shown are a version corrected to a dry basis from the original data collected from the literature.

843 Figure 13 shows the variation in the ignition rate with the air flux for some
 844 experimental results reported in the literature. To facilitate interpretation
 845 of the data, and given that the shape of the curve is similar to that of \dot{m}''_{ig} ,
 846 the variation in the burning rate is excluded from Figure 13. This figure also
 847 presents the change in bed stoichiometry with the air flux. The stoichiometric
 848 ratio (λ) in Figure 13 was estimated from the ratio between the stoichiometric
 849 ignition rate and the experimentally measured rate:

$$\lambda = \frac{\dot{m}''_{ig,sto}}{\dot{m}''_{ig}} \quad (8)$$

850 where, $\dot{m}''_{ig,sto}$ was calculated by the expression:

$$\dot{m}''_{ig,sto} = \frac{\dot{m}''_{air}}{[A/F]_{sto}} \quad (9)$$

851 As shown in Figure 13, at low air fluxes, in the region where \dot{m}''_{ig} propor-
 852 tionally increases with air flux, the bed stoichiometry remains almost uni-
 853 form. However, in the reaction-limited regime, even though \dot{m}''_{ig} continues to
 854 increase, the bed combustion evolves under increasingly lean conditions. Ex-
 855 perimental results have shown that the reaction zone thickness controls the
 856 bed stoichiometry, which is similarly governed by the char consumption rate
 857 [58]. In the oxygen-limited regime, the rise in \dot{m}''_{ig} , mainly in \dot{m}''_{bur} , regulates
 858 the bed stoichiometry, keeping it roughly uniform under very rich conditions.
 859 As the air flux increases, the char consumption rate increases, affecting the
 860 reaction zone thickness, which becomes thinner [142]. Because the char in-
 861 side the reaction zone decreases, more oxygen escapes from the bed without
 862 reacting, and consequently, combustion is carried out under stoichiometric
 863 conditions. This effect is more substantial in the reaction-limited regime and

864 increases quickly in the extinction regime.

865 Figure 13 also shows that the fuels develop their maximum ignition rates
866 under substoichiometric conditions in the regime controlled by the reaction.
867 Beyond this point, the bed reaction zone stoichiometry increases rapidly
868 while bed combustion enters the extinction regime (see Figure 14). However,
869 the ignition rate slightly varies in the case of coke combustion, which has a
870 lower volatile content than other fuels. During the two initial combustion
871 regimes, the level of CO is high. This level progressively decreases as the
872 airflow rate supplied to the bed increases [57, 131, 136, 137, 143]; in contrast,
873 the average concentration of CO₂ in flue gas can even reach a stable value
874 [65], even under substoichiometric conditions. Finally, before the air flux
875 reaches the extinction point, which stops combustion, CO₂ levels drop rapidly
876 because of the extinction of the reaction zone.

877 As shown in Figure 13, the ignition rates of some fuels, such as wood pel-
878 lets and high-temperature coke, are stable within the limits of the reaction-
879 limited regime and part of the extinction regime. This behaviour contrasts
880 with the straw ignition rate profile in Figure 13. Figure 15 correlates the max-
881 imum ignition rate with its respective stoichiometric ratio (λ_{cr}) of some fuels
882 in experimentally fixed-bed reactors along with the ratio between their initial
883 contents of volatile material and fixed carbon (VM/FC). λ_{cr} is defined by the
884 critical air flow rate. This figure reveals a positive correlation between the
885 volatile-material and fixed-carbon content ratios and the maximum ignition
886 rate. Furthermore, there is a negative trend between this critical value and
887 the corresponding stoichiometric ratio (critical stoichiometric ratio). Fuels
888 with higher volatile contents are more reactive, expel more energy in shorter

Figure 14: Total CO₂ and CO level variation with bed stoichiometry: ■ Straw [57], △ Forestry residues [65] (right y-axis), ◆ Hazardous wastes [133]

Figure 15: Maximum ignition rate, volatile-fixed carbon content ratio versus the critical stoichiometric ratio: 1. Textile residues [88], 2. Switchgrass [87], 3. Straw [87], 4. Cane leaves [83], 5. Wood [134], 6. Cardboard [88], 7. Almond shells [134], 8. Pine [134], 9. RDF [134], 10. High-temperature coke [138], 11. Poplar [134], 12. Olive stone [134] and 13. Brassica [134]

889 amounts of time, requiring lower airflow rates than fuels with more fixed
890 carbon [141]. However, these fuels experience flame instabilities during re-
891 actions after they reach $\dot{m}''_{a,cr}$. In contrast, as the content of fixed carbon
892 increases, it is necessary to increase airflow rates to reach the maximum ig-
893 nition rate (Figure 15), and there is high stability in the region limited by
894 reaction-limited and extinction regimes.

895 In practice, working with fuels with a stable reaction rate close to its
896 maximum value, close to the maximum ignition and consumption rate, is
897 desirable. The combustion of these fuels offers resilience to fluctuations in-
898 herent in boiler operation, such as variations in airflow and fuel feed rates
899 [134]. Fuels with very variable \dot{m}''_{ig} and \dot{m}''_{bur} , as agricultural residues, includ-
900 ing straw and pine pellets in Figure 13, might require robust control of the
901 primary air supply under the grate. Therefore, cocombustion with solid fuels
902 with higher fixed carbon contents is recommended to properly integrate agri-
903 cultural residues in thermal energy generation systems. In this way, problems
904 associated with flame instabilities may be reduced.

905 Nevertheless, the burning of agricultural residues around $\dot{m}''_{a,cr}$ presents
906 many challenges because of the higher temperatures. This condition increases
907 the risk of presenting issues related to the deposition of inorganic material on
908 burner heat transfer surfaces because of the high concentrations of alkalis and
909 chlorine in this type of biomass [67, 144]. Additionally, given the increased
910 oxygen availability as a consequence of high airflow rates, when biomass
911 combustion occurs between the regimes controlled by reaction and extinction,
912 the production of NO and the amount of entrained particles out of the bed
913 increase [145, 146].

914 *6.1.2. Staged air combustion*

915 Some works have studied the effect of air flux on fixed-bed combustion
916 with staged air and continuous fuel feeding [147]. These studies experimen-
917 tally demonstrated the existence of a combination of primary and secondary
918 air flows that enhance biomass combustion behaviour. The combination
919 maintains substoichiometric conditions in the bed region and supplies enough
920 secondary air to burn the fuel gases that escape from the bed. Fixing the
921 stoichiometric conditions in the bed region and increasing the total airflow
922 rate by supplying more secondary air allows the burning rate in the bed to
923 increase [142]. As discussed previously, when a fixed-bed burns with only
924 primary air, the convective dissipation effect of the airflow limits the ignition
925 and burning rates. Conversely, during bed combustion with staged air, the
926 secondary combustion region has high oxygen availability to burn the excess
927 volatile material and reduce soot production [148]. The heat released during
928 gas combustion offsets the heat dissipated from the bed by primary airflow.
929 The excess heat gained in the bed increases the ignition and burning rates
930 in the bed's reaction zone. However, as Junejo et al. [78] reported, the sec-
931 ondary air inlet port position plays an essential role in taking advantage of
932 the positive effects of staged air. Rogers [149] suggested this after perform-
933 ing fixed-bed combustion experiments with simulated refuse. According to
934 the experimental results of Junejo et al. [78], there is a maximum distance
935 between the bed level and the secondary air inlet beyond which the burning
936 rate, ignition front velocity, and bed temperature decrease.

937 Houshfar and collaborators reported that fuel-N conversion to NO is re-
938 duced under substoichiometric conditions in the bed region and overstoichio-

939 metric conditions in the secondary air zone. This effect is due to the low
940 stoichiometry in the bed and the high residence time of gases evolving from
941 the bed to the secondary zone, as previously explained [68, 115, 150]. Further-
942 more, lower combustion temperatures in the bed within the regime limited
943 by oxygen diminish the formation of inorganic vapours and the amount of
944 entrained char and ash particles [52, 67, 145, 146]. However, for a given fuel
945 or a fuel mixture, to optimize the operational behaviour of fixed-bed combus-
946 tion, it is necessary to investigate flue gas variation as a function of primary
947 and secondary air rate combinations.

948 *6.1.3. Air preheating temperature*

949 Preheating the oxidant medium increases the amount of energy released
950 from the fuel. This effect occurs because of the reduction in the sensible
951 thermal load of the oxidant medium, which is required to lead the fuel-
952 oxygen mixture to its ignition temperature. Therefore, the reactions are
953 intensified together with \dot{m}''_{ig} , \dot{m}''_{bur} , and reaction zone temperature during
954 fixed-bed combustion [98, 151].

955 Studies on air preheated as the oxidant medium show two combustion
956 behaviours that depend on the fuel pyrolysis temperature [152]. In the first
957 case, the air is preheated to temperatures much lower than the fuel pyrolysis
958 temperature. When air enters the bed, it transfers heat to the fuel layers
959 closest to the grate, drying the fuel particles. This effect propagates upwards
960 along the bed as a drying front. Nevertheless, the air stream temperature
961 decreases, and its moisture increases due to heat and mass transfer with fuel
962 particles [82]. The preheating temperature, fuel moisture content, and bed
963 height may negatively affect the bed combustion performance. van Kessel

964 et al. [82] reported that when highly moist fuels burn in a moving grate re-
965 actor, some moisture transported by air may condense in intermediate bed
966 layers, delaying ignition front propagation. The negative impact of preheat-
967 ing is present only before drying and ignition fronts intercept during their
968 propagation. This phenomenon was also reported by Vorotinskienė et al.
969 [153], who simulated the drying process during biomass-packed-bed combus-
970 tion experiments at different air flow preheating temperatures. After that,
971 there is a sharp increase in the ignition rate, and the previously dried fuel
972 layers ignite rapidly. van Kessel et al. [82] defined this effect as total com-
973 bustion.

974 The second situation occurs when the air preheating temperature is close
975 to the fuel pyrolysis temperature, approximately between 230 and 250 °C
976 [152]. As in the first case, a drying front propagates upwards. The air
977 stream continues to heat the particles remaining behind the drying front
978 until they reach pyrolysis temperature. After that, an upwards travelling
979 devolatilization front appears. The layers on the grate ignite, and an ignition
980 front propagates upwards. Some authors have defined this type of fixed-
981 bed combustion as upwards combustion [60, 154]. Among the advantages of
982 upwards combustion, we have the following:

- 983 1. Drying and pyrolysis stage separation from bed combustion. This effect
984 causes the propagation of the reaction zone along the bed to be less
985 dependent on the heterogeneity of the particles [60, 154]. The volatile
986 gases that escape from the bed may be burned by the addition of
987 secondary air.
- 988 2. Because of the fuel layers over the reaction zone, there is more re-

989 sistance to the combustion gases flowing through the bed, therefore,
990 reducing the emission of entrained particles, as reported by Markovic
991 et al. [60]

992 .

993 Despite the advantages of fixed-bed upwards combustion, this type of
994 combustion tends to be uncontrollable when air is used as an oxidant be-
995 cause of the high levels of volatile gases produced [60]. To avoid this effect,
996 Markovic et al. [60] recommended the use of a mixture of air and recircu-
997 lated flue gases. However, as there are few works in the literature concerning
998 this phenomenon, it is necessary to carry out more studies to implement this
999 technique in biomass combustion in fixed-bed reactors.

1000 *6.1.4. Oxidant medium composition*

1001 There are few works in the literature concerning the effect of oxidant
1002 medium composition on biomass combustion in fixed-bed laboratory-scale
1003 reactors. Nonetheless, these studies address two main themes: NO_x reduction
1004 [114, 155] and combustion behaviour [156]. In this section, we discuss the
1005 latter topic.

1006 The combustion behaviour of the fuel bed is sensitive to the oxygen con-
1007 centration and thermal properties of the gases that constitute the oxidant
1008 medium. Meng et al. [129] conducted combustion experiments on poplar
1009 sawdust in a fixed-bed reactor using different oxygen–nitrogen mixtures as
1010 the oxidant medium. They reported that the reaction zone temperature and
1011 combustion efficiency increase with the oxygen level in the oxidant medium.
1012 Tanui et al. [92] evaluated the effect of atmospheres composed of CO_2 and O_2

1013 mixtures on the propagation of the reaction zone during wood combustion.
1014 The measured reaction zone temperatures and the estimated ignition rates
1015 were lower than those observed when air was used as the oxidant medium.
1016 This effect is due to the specific heat of inert gases in the oxidant medium
1017 (CO_2 has a higher specific heat than N_2 at temperatures greater than 600 K).
1018 V M et al. [157] conducted combustion experiments on beds of agro-industrial
1019 waste pellets burned in oxidizing environments consisting of mixtures of oxy-
1020 gen with CO_2 or N_2 at different concentrations. The authors reported that
1021 the ignition front experienced instabilities in its propagation when the oxy-
1022 gen content exceeded 42% by volume. Under these conditions, the ignition
1023 front propagates discontinuously, "jumping" to deeper layers of fresh fuel
1024 while leaving behind particles still undergoing pyrolysis. The authors define
1025 this phenomenon as "flame jump" and highlight its negative implications for
1026 biomass gasification systems.

1027 The results above highlight the importance of the oxidizing medium's
1028 composition in thermoconversion projects of biomass in fixed-bed reactors.
1029 However, it is necessary to explore this phenomenon further, especially with
1030 respect to residual biomass, because of its highly heterogeneous properties
1031 and relevant role as a future fuel source for heat generation.

1032 Flue gas recirculation, or FGR, is one of the most utilized strategies for
1033 reducing NO_x emissions from biomass boilers. As biofuels are prone to have a
1034 greater proportion of molecule-bound nitrogen than coal in their composition,
1035 their combustion often leads to comparatively higher levels of nitrogen oxides.
1036 By substituting part of the intake air flow for chimney gas, the availability
1037 of oxygen in the reaction zone is reduced, limiting the formation of thermal

1038 NOx due to temperature control, and fuel-NOx due to the increased presence
1039 of carbon dioxide [155]. Pérez-Orozco et al. [158] linked the utilization of this
1040 strategy in an 18kW lab-scale facility to noticeable CO and PM reductions,
1041 whereas Polonini et al. [116] modified a 9 kW pellet stove to recirculate
1042 flue gas directly to the combustion chamber, achieving an 11% reduction
1043 in NOx emissions. Furthermore, this strategy was combined with oxy-fuel
1044 combustion to achieve very low CO and NO concentrations in the work of
1045 Sung et al. [159]. In oxy-fuel combustion a mixture of O₂ and CO₂ is used as
1046 an oxidizer with the aim of achieving an almost pure CO₂ stream on the flue
1047 gas, allowing techniques such as carbon sequestration to be more effective.
1048 This strategy has proven to be effective in reducing PM emissions in fixed-bed
1049 systems, as indicated in the studies of Wang et al. [160].

1050 Another possibility has been gaining traction in the last few years, consist-
1051 ing of the substitution of N₂ or CO₂ for H₂O, so-called oxy-steam combustion.
1052 This technique is well studied in the field of coal, although biomass-centred
1053 studies can also be found in smaller numbers. Díez et al. [161] studied the
1054 effects of including up to 40% H₂O in the combustion of torrefied biomass on
1055 its own and blending with coal and reported that 25% H₂O was the optimum
1056 point for NO reduction and maximization of the degree of conversion. This
1057 confirms the findings of Li et al. [162], where the total substitution of N₂
1058 by H₂O resulted in an acceleration of the burning rate of the feedstocks and
1059 reduced NO emissions. Other studies performed with alternative, low-grade
1060 biofuels such as vine pruning, or corn waste are in line with these findings,
1061 suggesting that while the presence of H₂O has a noticeable effect on nitrogen
1062 oxides, it does not influence the release of CO and CO₂ [163, 164].

1063 *6.2. Effects of particle size and bed physical properties*

1064 The combustion of a single particle depends on its characteristics, such
1065 as size, density, shape, and physical properties. Conversely, when a group of
1066 particles burns together, as in packed-bed combustion, the extent of the par-
1067 ticle arrangement in the bed also governs the combustion behaviour. This
1068 influence overlaps with the effects of a single particle's properties. Conse-
1069 quently, difficulties arise in distinguishing the impact of individual and pack-
1070 ing properties on the combustion of beds composed of particles with different
1071 geometric characteristics.

1072 Despite the limitations caused by the strong relationships between indi-
1073 vidual particle dimensions and packed-bed properties, various authors have
1074 achieved significant results regarding the effect of particle geometry varia-
1075 tion on fixed-bed combustion behaviour. In this section, we first present the
1076 effects of the fuel particle size distribution. Then, the effects of the packing
1077 parameters on the porosity and bulk density are discussed.

1078 *6.2.1. Bed's particle size distribution effect*

1079 One of the main effects of increasing fuel particle size over fixed-bed
1080 combustion behaviour is the reduction of \dot{m}''_{ig} and \dot{m}''_{bur} , as shown in Figure 16.
1081 For a given airflow rate, in beds composed of larger particles, because of the
1082 internal temperature gradients, each fresh fuel particle inside the reaction
1083 zone increases its temperature more slowly than in beds of small particles;
1084 consequently, the particles go through drying and pyrolysis stages at low
1085 rates. As the bed particle size increases, the availability of oxygen supplied
1086 by the air supply increases in relation to the surface area available for heat
1087 and mass transfer. This phenomenon reduces the amounts of combustible

Figure 16: Ignition rate variation with particle size for different biomass samples: Pine pellets [126] ($\dot{m}''_{air} = 0.56 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$), pine bark [132] ($\dot{m}''_{air} = 0.15 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$), and willow [165] ($\dot{m}''_{air} = 0.10 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$).

1088 gases emitted from the bed [83, 143, 165, 166] (Figure 17) and the levels
 1089 of entrained bed particles, but this condition promotes a reduction in the
 1090 reaction zone temperature [61]. Therefore, the ignition rate is reduced.

1091 An internal reaction front forms inside each particle while the ignition
 1092 front propagates along the bed. Because \dot{m}''_{bur} is lower than \dot{m}''_{ig} , during bed
 1093 combustion, the reaction zone thickness increases along with the residual
 1094 char particles until the end of the process [167]. Additionally, because oxygen
 1095 availability increases with increasing particle size, more fuel-N is converted to
 1096 NO [166, 168]. In some cases, when the bed is composed of large particles, the
 1097 whole fixed-bed combustion process is fragmented, resulting in the isolated
 1098 combustion of each particle [83].

Figure 17: Effect of particle size on CO emission during fixed-bed combustion of willow [165] ($\dot{m}''_{air} = 0.10 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$), corn stalks [166] ($\dot{m}''_{air} = 0.053 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$) and Hazardous wastes [143].

Figure 18: Ignition rate variation with bulk density during fixed-bed combustion of different biomasses. (a) Pine bark: ∇ 2–6 mm ($\rho_b = 189.6 \text{ kg/m}^3$), \blacktriangledown 6–9 mm ($\rho_b = 171.5 \text{ kg/m}^3$), \diamond 9–12 mm ($\rho_b = 165.7 \text{ kg/m}^3$) [132]; (b) \circ Loose cane fibres ($\rho_b = 46.4 \text{ kg/m}^3$), \bullet Dense cane fibres ($\rho_b = 77.4 \text{ kg/m}^3$) [83]; (c) \blacktriangle Cut straw ($\rho_b = 85.0 \text{ kg/m}^3$), \triangle whole straw ($\rho_b = 50.0 \text{ kg/m}^3$) [57].

1099 *6.2.2. Bed packing properties effect*

1100 During fixed-bed combustion of uniformly packed particles with the same
1101 density (ρ_p), the heat released from the reaction zone attains fresh particles
1102 by radiation. In beds with high porosities, the radiated heat may travel long
1103 distances, so the reaction zone thickness is greater than that observed in low
1104 porosity beds [91, 156]. Under these conditions, the heat intensity received
1105 by every particle in close layers decreases. Thus, the ignition and burning
1106 rates are lower in bulky beds than in more compact beds [49, 61, 90, 169], as
1107 shown in Figure 18-(a).

1108 Bed porosity also affects the fixed-bed combustion range of usable air-
1109 flow rates, i.e., the range of airflow rate values within which the reaction
1110 takes place (Figure 18-(a)). In beds of small particles, because combustion
1111 reactions are more intense due to the higher surface area and lower porosity,
1112 large amounts of volatiles are released quickly. Figure 17 shows the strong
1113 influence of particle size on CO emission. Hence, for a fixed airflow rate, the
1114 reaction zone stoichiometry is lower than that observed in beds of larger par-
1115 ticles with higher porosity [126]. The porosity reduction in the bed reduces
1116 the airflow rate required to quench the bed (Figure 18-(a)).

1117 Different behaviours occur during fixed-bed combustion experiments of
1118 thin-light particles such as straw, leaves, and grasses [57, 83]. As shown
1119 in Figure 18-(b) and (c), the ignition rate is higher in beds with lower ρ_b
1120 (higher porosity) at a fixed airflow rate. Some authors attributed this effect
1121 to channelling. Channelling is the consequence of an uneven distribution
1122 of particle size that forms interconnected spots of high local porosity [128,
1123 170], mainly near reactor walls [148], which serve as shortcuts for air and

1124 gas flow. Because the airflow rate is higher at these locations, combustion
1125 reactions are more intense, and temperature variation along the bed cross-
1126 section is considered. This phenomenon increases the ignition front speed,
1127 which rapidly reaches the grate even when the particles are under ignition
1128 [85–87]. However, the burning rate has been shown to be unaffected by
1129 the abrupt increase in \dot{m}''_{ig} , as Khor et al. [87] noted. Beds composed of
1130 untreated fuel particles exhibit the above effects. For example, Zhou et al.
1131 [57] (Figure 18-(c)), Milijković [56] and Khor et al. [87] used long straw fibres
1132 in their experiments. The wide heterogeneity among bed particles establishes
1133 nonuniform packing, which enables channelling to occur [87].

1134 Tanui et al. [156] reported a similar effect of bed porosity on the ignition
1135 front in beds composed of fine wood particles (wood and sawdust). These
1136 results are interesting because the beds studied by Tanui and collaborators
1137 presented higher bulk density values – between 390 - 597 kg/m³, than did the
1138 biomasses discussed in the above paragraph (see Figure 18). Such an increase
1139 in \dot{m}''_{ig} reached a maximum value for a defined critical bed porosity. Beyond
1140 this critical bed porosity, the ignition rate decreased [156] because of the
1141 increase in the convective dissipative effect. Nevertheless, more studies are
1142 needed to gain complete insight into the effect of bed porosity on fixed-bed
1143 performance.

1144 Figure 18-(b) and (c) also show that although \dot{m}''_{ig} decreases with by in-
1145 creasing ρ_b , the combustion is more stable than untreated biomass particles
1146 are. When the biomass particle size is homogenized by size reduction pro-
1147 cessing, the likelihood of channelling formation decreases. Additionally, a
1148 uniform particle size allows a better distribution of the airflow in the bed.

1149 In this way, the ignition front stably propagates along the bed. However,
1150 the type of solid fuel, as shown in Figure 18-(b) and (c), is characterized by
1151 a low density (ρ_p). Therefore, the positive effects of particle size reduction
1152 are considerable above some limit size of the particle. Below this dimen-
1153 sion, losses by particle entrainment may be significant enough to affect the
1154 fixed-bed combustion efficiency.

1155 In general, as shown in Figure 18, bed porosity (or bulk density) may
1156 affect fixed-bed combustion in two ways, each of which depends on the con-
1157 figuration and density of fuel particles: (1) thin-light and (2) coarse particles.
1158 The first group includes most agricultural residues, such as straw, leaves, and
1159 grasses; the latter consists of particles with either cubic, cylindrical, or semi-
1160 spherical shapes, such as coal and wood particles. In beds composed of
1161 particles from both groups, stable and resilient combustion can be obtained
1162 [126, 171]. From a bed property perspective, to harness the high availabil-
1163 ity and energetic potential of agricultural residues, cocombustion with the
1164 biomass of the second group is a promising option.

1165 *6.3. Moisture content effect*

1166 The data plotted in Figures 19 and 20 correspond to the experimental
1167 results of fixed-bed combustion with air supplied at room temperature. For a
1168 fixed airflow rate, increasing the fuel moisture level slows both \dot{m}''_{ig} and \dot{m}''_{bur} ,
1169 which increases the reaction time. This effect occurs because the energy
1170 required to dry each particle in the bed reaction zone increases, which reduces
1171 its heating rate to reach the ignition temperature [97, 136].

1172 The moisture level effect is more intense in \dot{m}''_{ig} than \dot{m}''_{bur} , as shown
1173 in Figure 20. This effect on both parameters suggests that the reaction

Figure 19: Influence of fuel particle moisture on the ignition rate for different biomasses: Wood chips [172] ($\dot{m}'_{air} = 0.15 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$), wood pellets [134], thin wood chips [49] ($\dot{m}'_{air} = 0.11 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$), and beechwood chips [106] ($\dot{m}'_{air} = 0.014 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$).

Figure 20: Comparison between ignition rates and burning rates with moisture level: Wood chips ($\dot{m}'_{air} = 0.15 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$) [172] and beechwood ($\dot{m}'_{air} = 0.014 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$) [106].

Figure 21: Influence of moisture level on bed combustion stoichiometry: Municipal solid wastes [136], wood chips [172].

1174 zone thickness decreases as the moisture level of the fuel particles increases.
 1175 Hence, an increase in moisture promotes the char consumption rate during
 1176 the stable propagation phase of the reaction zone [97, 151, 172]. This effect
 1177 can be explained as follows: the particle heating rate influences its pyrolysis
 1178 rate. The pyrolysis rate affects both \dot{m}''_{ig} and \dot{m}''_{bur} ; however the former is
 1179 more sensitive to this parameter variation [61, 97]. At a fixed airflow rate,
 1180 lower amounts of volatile gases increase oxygen availability to consume the
 1181 char formed during the stable propagation phase of the reaction zone, as
 1182 illustrated in Figure 21. As the moisture level of fuel particles increases,
 1183 the reaction zone becomes thinner, and there is less residual char in the last
 1184 fixed-bed combustion phase [97]. Consequently, the reaction zone propagates
 1185 along the bed more stably, and the amount of nonburned gases evolving out
 1186 of the bed decreases.

1187 The reduction in the pyrolysis rate with increasing moisture level also

1188 affects the combustion regime region of the bed. As reported both in both
1189 experimental [134] and numerical results [136], the critical air flux for drier
1190 fuels is greater than the observed for wetter fuels. Additionally, the usable air
1191 flux range is reduced as ω increases. Then, a wetter fuel reaches extinction
1192 at lower \dot{m}'_{air} .

1193 The fuel moisture level reduces the reaction zone temperature because a
1194 higher thermal load is required to evaporate the water and heat the steam
1195 released [172]. Nevertheless, as illustrated in Figure 22, the maximum com-
1196 bustion temperature (T_{max}) is unaltered at low moisture levels, when ω varies
1197 from 20% – 30% [61, 97, 134]. At a relatively high moisture level, the max-
1198 imum combustion temperature in the reaction zone decreases until the hu-
1199 midity reaches a certain level. From that level, T_{max} remains unaltered up to
1200 a high humidity level such that combustion is unsustainable. Because char
1201 and volatiles react in a narrower region, those reactions counterbalance the
1202 heat consumed by the moisture, keeping the temperature roughly constant.

1203 Fuel moisture limits the combustion performance because it increases the
1204 water's latent and sensible energy demands and extends the total combus-
1205 tion time. However, experimental evidence has demonstrated that fixed-bed
1206 combustion of highly wet fuels occurs under stable temperatures and reac-
1207 tion front propagation conditions. This effect can be beneficial for com-
1208 busting highly humid fuels such as agricultural residues and MSW in fixed-
1209 bed combustion reactors. These types of fuels are continuously produced
1210 throughout the year at low costs. The availability of these fuels may off-
1211 set moisture-related energy loss to produce inexpensive and environmentally
1212 friendly thermal energy.

Figure 22: Maximum bed combustion temperature variation with fuel moisture level: ■ woodchips [61], ▽ wood pellets [134], △ municipal solid wastes [97], and ▲ corn straw [151]

1213 7. Conclusions

1214 Given their broad flexibility to burn highly heterogeneous fuels, grate
 1215 burners are mainly used for biomass combustion. Despite fixed-bed com-
 1216 bustion being an old technique used for thermal energy generation, there
 1217 are challenges associated with direct biomass combustion. To address these
 1218 challenges, over the past few decades, scientific efforts have yielded many ex-
 1219 perimental investigations concerning biomass fixed-bed combustion-related
 1220 phenomena. The present work consolidated, summarized, and discussed
 1221 the knowledge in the literature associated with packed-bed combustion in
 1222 laboratory-scale set-ups. In addition, the main parameters used as indica-
 1223 tors of bed combustion performance were defined, and the main operational
 1224 factors that influence the reaction performance were described.

1225 Fixed-bed combustion occurs in the reaction zone. Inside this narrow
 1226 region bounded by the ignition front and bed level, all thermochemical trans-

1227 formations of the fuel particles proceed. During fixed-bed combustion, the
1228 chemical reaction performance manifests through the variation in the reaction
1229 zone thickness. The combination of the reaction zone stoichiometry, packing
1230 degree, fuel particle morphology, and physicochemical properties dominates
1231 the reaction zone thickness. The main effects of these fixed-bed parameters
1232 are summarized as follows:

- 1233 - The reaction zone stoichiometry depends on the difference between the
1234 reaction rate and the oxidant medium supply rate. The latter includes
1235 the oxidant's thermodynamic state and flow dynamics across the bed.
1236 In the absence of a secondary oxidant feed, such a difference establishes
1237 three characteristic regimes under which fixed-bed combustion occur:
1238 (i) oxygen-limited regime, (ii) reaction-limited regime, and (iii) extinc-
1239 tion regime. However, staged air combustion significantly improves the
1240 performance of the reaction zone, including increasing the ignition and
1241 burning rates and reducing NO_x emissions. These improvements arise
1242 from an appropriate combination of primary and secondary air supplies.
1243 In addition, the input of primary preheated air increases the ignition
1244 and burning rates by decreasing the sensible enthalpy required to heat
1245 fresh particles below the ignition front to the ignition temperature.
- 1246 - Fuel particle morphology and physicochemical properties control the
1247 inwards heat transfer and, consequently, the evolution of the sequential
1248 particle combustion stages. The bed's packing level is measured by its
1249 porosity, which affects the emitted heat distribution and the extent of
1250 the oxidant flow dissipative effect. Hence, these properties govern the
1251 stability of the reaction zone.

1252 - The initial fuel moisture content influences the reaction zone behaviour.
1253 This parameter impacts combustion heat harnessing. The experimental
1254 results collected in this work suggest that although the increase in the
1255 fuel moisture level narrows the reaction zone thickness, the combustion
1256 of the bed becomes more stable. Additionally, the amount of unreacted
1257 fuel gas expelled from the bed is reduced.

1258 One of the main lacks identified in this review is related to the variation
1259 in the bed level position during reaction zone propagation. The difficulty in
1260 measuring this parameter without interfering with heat transfer inside the
1261 reaction zone is the main reason for the small number of studies available
1262 in the literature. Nevertheless, knowing the instant bed height would lead
1263 to estimation of other parameters to characterize the fixed-bed combustion
1264 performance, such as the bulk density variation, char consumption rate, and
1265 reaction zone thickness.

1266 Because of their abundant annual and geographic availability, agricul-
1267 tural residues are promising alternatives to fossil fuels. Moreover, employing
1268 agricultural residues as thermal energy sources leads to benefits that are
1269 consistent with current sustainable commitments worldwide. Despite these
1270 advantages, the direct combustion of these biomasses in grate furnaces has
1271 drawbacks related to the vast diversity in the physicochemical properties of
1272 agricultural residues, which affects their combustion efficiency and stability.
1273 However, the cocombustion of fuels with contrasting characteristics might
1274 improve fixed-bed performance. Contrasting characteristics refer to oppos-
1275 ing properties in terms of particle size, packing properties, and the content of
1276 volatiles or fixed carbon. Nevertheless, it is necessary to carry out additional

1277 studies to address this possibility, which would allow the establishment of cri-
1278 teria for the suitable integration of agricultural residues as energy sources.

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1284 130639/2019-2, Brazil.

1285 **References**

- 1286 [1] L. Pelkmans, IEA Bioenergy Countries' Report – Update 2021, Tech-
1287 nical Report, IEA Bioenergy, Paris, 2021.
- 1288 [2] V. Lenz, N. Szarka, M. Jordan, D. Thrän, Status and Perspec-
1289 tives of Biomass Use for Industrial Process Heat for Industrialized
1290 Countries, *Chemical Engineering & Technology* 43 (2020) 1469–1484.
1291 doi:10.1002/ceat.202000077.
- 1292 [3] IEA – International Energy Agency, *World Energy Balances 2022 –*
1293 *Total Energy Supply by source, World 1990-2020*, 2021.
- 1294 [4] K. Rayaprolu, *Boilers for Power and Process*, CRC press, 2009.
- 1295 [5] E. K. Vakkilainen, *Steam Generation from Biomass: Construction and*
1296 *Design of Large Boilers*, Butterworth-Heinemann, 2016.

- 1297 [6] E. B. Woodruff, H. B. Lammers, T. F. Lammers, Steam Plant Opera-
1298 tion, 10th Edition, McGraw-Hill Education, 2017.
- 1299 [7] J. Koppejan, S. Van Loo, The Handbook of Biomass Combustion and
1300 Co-Firing, Routledge, 2012.
- 1301 [8] Ministerio de Minas e Energia, Resenha Energética Brasileira 2020,
1302 MME. Brasília (2021) 31.
- 1303 [9] C. Yin, L. A. Rosendahl, S. K. Kær, Grate-firing of biomass for heat
1304 and power production, Progress in Energy and Combustion Science 34
1305 (2008) 725–754. doi:10.1016/j.pecs.2008.05.002.
- 1306 [10] H. Khodaei, Y. M. Al-Abdeli, F. Guzzomi, G. H. Yeoh, An overview
1307 of processes and considerations in the modelling of fixed-bed biomass
1308 combustion, Energy 88 (2015) 946–972. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2015.
1309 05.099.
- 1310 [11] A. Dernbecher, A. Dieguez-Alonso, A. Ortwein, F. Tabet, Review
1311 on modelling approaches based on computational fluid dynamics for
1312 biomass combustion systems: Focus on fixed bed and moving grate
1313 systems, Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery 9 (2019) 129–182. doi:10.
1314 1007/s13399-019-00370-z.
- 1315 [12] R. P. Van Der Lans, LT. Pedersen, A. Jensen, P. Glarborg, K. Dam-
1316 Johansen, Modelling and experiments of straw combustion in a grate
1317 furnace, Biomass and Bioenergy 19 (2000) 199–208. doi:10.1016/
1318 S0961-9534(00)00033-7.

- 1319 [13] L. Liang, R. Sun, J. Fei, S. Wu, X. Liu, K. Dai, N. Yao, Experimental
1320 study on effects of moisture content on combustion characteristics of
1321 simulated municipal solid wastes in a fixed bed, *Bioresource technology*
1322 99 (2008) 7238–7246. doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2007.12.061.
- 1323 [14] E. J. S. Mitchell, A. R. Lea-Langton, J. M. Jones, A. Williams,
1324 P. Layden, R. Johnson, The impact of fuel properties on the emis-
1325 sions from the combustion of biomass and other solid fuels in a fixed
1326 bed domestic stove, *Fuel Processing Technology* 142 (2016) 115–123.
1327 doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2015.09.031.
- 1328 [15] S. Zapata, P. Canalís, J. Royo, M. Gómez, C. Bartolomé, Combustion
1329 Performance of Agropellets in an Experimental Fixed Bed Reactor
1330 versus a Commercial Grate Boiler. Validation of Ash Behavior, *ACS*
1331 *Omega* 8 (2023) 29485–29499. doi:10.1021/acsomega.3c03201.
- 1332 [16] M. Recman, J. Hájek, Experimental reactor for analysing biomass
1333 combustion properties, *Chemical Engineering Transactions* 18 (2009)
1334 977–982. doi:10.3303/CET0918160.
- 1335 [17] S. A. El-Sayed, M. A. Ismail, M. E. Mostafa, Thermal decomposition
1336 and combustion characteristics of biomass materials using TG/DTG at
1337 different high heating rates and sizes in the air, *Environmental Progress*
1338 *& Sustainable Energy* 38 (2019) 13124. doi:10.1002/ep.13124.
- 1339 [18] R. Barzegar, A. Yozgatligil, H. Olgun, A. T. Atimtay, TGA and kinetic
1340 study of different torrefaction conditions of wood biomass under air and

- oxy-fuel combustion atmospheres, *Journal of the Energy Institute* 93
(2020) 889–898. doi:10.1016/j.joei.2019.08.001.
- [19] J. J. Rico, R. Pérez-Orozco, D. Patiño Vilas, J. Porteiro, TG/DSC and kinetic parametrization of the combustion of agricultural and forestry residues, *Biomass and Bioenergy* 162 (2022) 106485. doi:10.1016/j.biombioe.2022.106485.
- [20] J. J. Saastamoinen, M. J. Aho, V. L. Linna, Simultaneous pyrolysis and char combustion, *Fuel* 72 (1993) 599–609. doi:10.1016/0016-2361(93)90571-I.
- [21] Y. A. Levendis, K. Joshi, R. Khatami, A. F. Sarofim, Combustion behavior in air of single particles from three different coal ranks and from sugarcane bagasse, *Combustion and Flame* 158 (2011) 452–465. doi:10.1016/j.combustflame.2010.09.007.
- [22] P. E. Mason, L. I. Darvell, J. M. Jones, M. Pourkashanian, A. Williams, Single particle flame-combustion studies on solid biomass fuels, *Fuel* 151 (2015) 21–30. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2014.11.088.
- [23] C. Mock, H. Lee, S. Choi, V. Manovic, Combustion Behavior of Relatively Large Pulverized Biomass Particles at Rapid Heating Rates, *Energy & Fuels* 30 (2016) 10809–10822. doi:10.1021/acs.energyfuels.6b01457.
- [24] A. Panahi, Y. A. Levendis, N. Vorobiev, M. Schiemann, Direct observations on the combustion characteristics of Miscanthus and Beechwood

- 1363 biomass including fusion and spherodization, *Fuel Processing Technol-*
1364 *ogy* 166 (2017) 41–49. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2017.05.029.
- 1365 [25] J. Riaza, J. Gibbins, H. Chalmers, Ignition and combustion of single
1366 particles of coal and biomass, *Fuel* 202 (2017) 650–655. doi:10.1016/
1367 j.fuel.2017.04.011.
- 1368 [26] L. Shan, M. Kong, T. D. Bennet, A. C. Sarroza, C. Eastwick, D. Sun,
1369 G. Lu, Y. Yan, H. Liu, Studies on combustion behaviours of single
1370 biomass particles using a visualization method, *Biomass and Bioenergy*
1371 109 (2018) 54–60. doi:10.1016/j.biombioe.2017.12.008.
- 1372 [27] F. A. Williams, *Combustion Theory*, CRC Press, 2018.
- 1373 [28] S. Turns, *An Introduction to Combustion Third Edition*, McGraw-Hill
1374 Education, 2011.
- 1375 [29] S. A. El-Sayed, M. E. Mostafa, T. M. Khass, E. H. Noseir, M. A.
1376 Ismail, Combustion and mass loss behavior and characteristics of a
1377 single biomass pellet positioning at different orientations in a fixed bed
1378 reactor, *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery* (2023). doi:10.1007/
1379 s13399-023-03767-z.
- 1380 [30] Y. B. Yang, V. N. Sharifi, J. Swithenbank, Numerical Simulation of the
1381 Burning Characteristics of Thermally-Thick Biomass Fuels in Packed-
1382 Beds, *Process Safety and Environmental Protection* 83 (2005) 549–558.
1383 doi:10.1205/psep.04284.
- 1384 [31] A. K. Biswas, K. Umeki, Simplification of devolatilization models for
1385 thermally-thick particles: Differences between wood logs and pellets,

- 1386 Chemical Engineering Journal 274 (2015) 181–191. doi:10.1016/j.
1387 cej.2015.03.131.
- 1388 [32] R. Mehrabian, S. Zahirovic, R. Scharler, I. Obernberger, S. Kleditzsch,
1389 S. Wirtz, V. Scherer, H. Lu, L. L. Baxter, A CFD model for ther-
1390 mal conversion of thermally thick biomass particles, Fuel Processing
1391 Technology 95 (2012) 96–108. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2011.11.021.
- 1392 [33] B. Tian, Y. Qiao, L. Bai, F. Liu, Y. Tian, K. Xie, Separation and
1393 structural characterization of groups from a high-volatile bituminous
1394 coal based on multiple techniques, Fuel Processing Technology 159
1395 (2017) 386–395. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2017.01.043.
- 1396 [34] Y. Lin, Y. Qin, D. Ma, Z. Duan, Pore structure, adsorptivity and
1397 influencing factors of high-volatile bituminous coal rich in inertinite,
1398 Fuel 293 (2021) 120418. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2021.120418.
- 1399 [35] D. Sha, Y. Li, X. Zhou, J. Zhang, H. Zhang, J. Yu, Influence of Volatile
1400 Content on the Explosion Characteristics of Coal Dust, ACS Omega 6
1401 (2021) 27150–27157. doi:10.1021/acsomega.1c03803.
- 1402 [36] C. Zhou, G. Liu, S. Cheng, T. Fang, P. K. S. Lam, Thermochemical
1403 and trace element behavior of coal gangue, agricultural biomass and
1404 their blends during co-combustion, Bioresource Technology 166 (2014)
1405 243–251. doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2014.05.076.
- 1406 [37] A. Magdziarz, M. Wilk, Thermogravimetric study of biomass, sewage
1407 sludge and coal combustion, Energy Conversion and Management 75
1408 (2013) 425–430. doi:10.1016/j.enconman.2013.06.016.

- 1409 [38] M. A. Saeed, G. E. Andrews, H. N. Phylaktou, B. M. Gibbs, Global
1410 kinetics of the rate of volatile release from biomasses in comparison to
1411 coal, *Fuel* 181 (2016) 347–357. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2016.04.123.
- 1412 [39] A. Williams, J. M. Jones, L. Ma, M. Pourkashanian, Pollutants from
1413 the combustion of solid biomass fuels, *Progress in Energy and Combustion
1414 Science* 38 (2012) 113–137. doi:10.1016/j.pecs.2011.10.001.
- 1415 [40] D. J. Nowakowski, J. M. Jones, R. M. D. Brydson, A. B. Ross, Potas-
1416 sium catalysis in the pyrolysis behaviour of short rotation willow cop-
1417 pice, *Fuel* 86 (2007) 2389–2402. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2007.01.026.
- 1418 [41] Q. Guo, Z. Cheng, G. Chen, B. Yan, L. Hou, F. Ronsse, Optimal
1419 strategy for clean and efficient biomass combustion based on ash de-
1420 position tendency and kinetic analysis, *Journal of Cleaner Production*
1421 271 (2020) 122529. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122529.
- 1422 [42] J. M. Jones, L. I. Darvell, T. G. Bridgeman, M. Pourkashanian,
1423 A. Williams, An investigation of the thermal and catalytic behaviour
1424 of potassium in biomass combustion, *Proceedings of the Combustion
1425 Institute* 31 (2007) 1955–1963. doi:10.1016/j.proci.2006.07.093.
- 1426 [43] A. Saddawi, J. M. Jones, A. Williams, Influence of alkali metals on
1427 the kinetics of the thermal decomposition of biomass, *Fuel Processing
1428 Technology* 104 (2012) 189–197. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2012.05.014.
- 1429 [44] R. Fahmi, A. V. Bridgwater, L. I. Darvell, J. M. Jones, N. Yates,
1430 S. Thain, I. S. Donnison, The effect of alkali metals on combustion

- 1431 and pyrolysis of *Lolium* and *Festuca* grasses, switchgrass and willow,
1432 *Fuel* 86 (2007) 1560–1569. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2006.11.030.
- 1433 [45] R. Khatami, C. Stivers, K. Joshi, Y. A. Levendis, A. F. Sarofim, Com-
1434 bustion behavior of single particles from three different coal ranks and
1435 from sugar cane bagasse in O₂/N₂ and O₂/CO₂ atmospheres, *Combustion and Flame* 159 (2012) 1253–1271. doi:10.1016/j.combustflame.
1436 2011.09.009.
- 1437
- 1438 [46] M. L. Hobbs, P. T. Radulovic, L. D. Smoot, Combustion and gasifica-
1439 tion of coals in fixed-beds, *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*
1440 19 (1993) 505–586. doi:10.1016/0360-1285(93)90003-W.
- 1441 [47] M. Hupa, O. Karlström, E. Vainio, Biomass combustion technology
1442 development – It is all about chemical details, *Proceedings of the*
1443 *Combustion Institute* 36 (2017) 113–134. doi:10.1016/j.proci.2016.
1444 06.152.
- 1445 [48] H. Wang, X. Jiang, M. Zhang, Y. Ma, H. Liu, S. Wu, A new
1446 Fluidization–Suspension combustion technology for coal water slurry,
1447 *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification* 49
1448 (2010) 1017–1024. doi:10.1016/j.cep.2010.07.009.
- 1449 [49] J. J. Saastamoinen, M. Horttanainen, P. Sarkomaa, Ignition Wave
1450 Propagation and Release of Volatiles in Beds of Wood Particles,
1451 *Combustion Science and Technology* 165 (2001) 41–60. doi:10.1080/
1452 00102200108935825.

- 1453 [50] M. Rönnbäck, M. Axell, L. Gustavsson, H. Thunman, B. Lecher, Com-
1454 bustion Processes in a Biomass Fuel Bed-Experimental Results, in:
1455 Progress in Thermochemical Biomass Conversion, John Wiley & Sons,
1456 Ltd, 2008, pp. 743–757. doi:10.1002/9780470694954.ch59.
- 1457 [51] Y. Niu, H. Tan, S. Hui, Ash-related issues during biomass combus-
1458 tion: Alkali-induced slagging, silicate melt-induced slagging (ash fu-
1459 sion), agglomeration, corrosion, ash utilization, and related counter-
1460 measures, Progress in Energy and Combustion Science 52 (2016) 1–61.
1461 doi:10.1016/j.pecs.2015.09.003.
- 1462 [52] J. Oman, M. Tacer, M. Tuma, Overfeed fixed-bed combustion of
1463 wood, Bioresource technology 67 (1999) 139–147. doi:10.1016/S0960-
1464 8524(98)00111-4.
- 1465 [53] A. Price-Allison, A. R. Lea-Langton, E. J. S. Mitchell, B. Gudka, J. M.
1466 Jones, P. E. Mason, A. Williams, Emissions performance of high mois-
1467 ture wood fuels burned in a residential stove, Fuel 239 (2019) 1038–
1468 1045. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2018.11.090.
- 1469 [54] D. Maxwell, B. A. Gudka, J. M. Jones, A. Williams, Emissions from
1470 the combustion of torrefied and raw biomass fuels in a domestic heating
1471 stove, Fuel Processing Technology 199 (2020) 106266. doi:10.1016/j.
1472 fuproc.2019.106266.
- 1473 [55] JEL. Rogers, AF. Sarofim, JB. Howard, Effect of underfire air rate
1474 on a burning simulated refuse bed, in: Proceedings] ASME National
1475 Incinerator Conference, New York, 1972, pp. 135–44.

- 1476 [56] B. M. Milijković, Experimental Facility for analysis of biomass com-
1477 bustion characteristics, *Thermal Science* 19 (2015).
- 1478 [57] H. Zhou, A. D. Jensen, P. Glarborg, P. A. Jensen, A. Kavaliauskas,
1479 Numerical modeling of straw combustion in a fixed bed, *Fuel* 84 (2005)
1480 389–403. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2004.09.020.
- 1481 [58] J. Porteiro, D. Patino, J. Collazo, E. Granada, J. Moran, JL. Miguez,
1482 Experimental analysis of the ignition front propagation of several
1483 biomass fuels in a fixed-bed combustor, *Fuel* 89 (2010) 26–35.
1484 doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2009.01.024.
- 1485 [59] R. Mehrabian, A. Shiehnejadhesar, R. Scharler, I. Obernberger, Multi-
1486 physics modelling of packed bed biomass combustion, *Fuel* 122 (2014)
1487 164–178. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2014.01.027.
- 1488 [60] M. Markovic, E. A. Bramer, G. Brem, Experimental investigation of
1489 wood combustion in a fixed bed with hot air, *Waste Management* 34
1490 (2014) 49–62. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2013.09.021.
- 1491 [61] J. J. Saastamoinen, R. Taipale, M. Horttanainen, P. Sarkomaa, Propa-
1492 gation of the ignition front in beds of wood particles, *Combustion and*
1493 *Flame* 123 (2000) 214–226. doi:10.1016/S0010-2180(00)00144-9.
- 1494 [62] H.-J. Gehrman, T. Kolb, H. Seifert, F. Mark, M. Frankenhaeuser,
1495 A. Schanssema, K. Wittstock, J. Kolb, Synergies between biomass
1496 and solid recovered fuel in energy conversion processes, *Environmental*
1497 *Engineering Science* 27 (2010) 557–567. doi:10.1089/ees.2009.0373.

- 1498 [63] Y. A. Lenis, A. F. Agudelo, J. F. Pérez, Analysis of statistical
1499 repeatability of a fixed bed downdraft biomass gasification facility,
1500 Applied Thermal Engineering 51 (2013) 1006–1016. doi:10.1016/j.
1501 applthermaleng.2012.09.046.
- 1502 [64] T. Eapen, R. Blackadar, R. H. Essenhigh, Kinetics of gasification in
1503 a combustion pot: A comparison of theory and experiment, Symposi-
1504 um (International) on Combustion 16 (1977) 515–522. doi:10.1016/
1505 S0082-0784(77)80348-2.
- 1506 [65] B. Olanders, N.-E. Gunnars, Some aspects of the formation of ni-
1507 tric oxide during the combustion of biomass fuels in a laboratory fur-
1508 nace, Biomass and Bioenergy 6 (1994) 443–451. doi:10.1016/0961-
1509 9534(95)90406-L.
- 1510 [66] J. T. Kuo, W.-S. Hsu, T.-C. Yo, Effect of air distribution on solid fuel
1511 bed combustion, Journal of energy resources technology 119 (1997)
1512 120–128. doi:doi:10.1115/1.2794975.
- 1513 [67] H. Wiinikka, R. Gebart, Critical Parameters for Particle Emissions in
1514 Small-Scale Fixed-Bed Combustion of Wood Pellets, Energy & Fuels
1515 18 (2004) 897–907. doi:10.1021/ef030173k.
- 1516 [68] E. Houshfar, Ø. Skreiberg, T. Løvås, D. Todorović, L. Sørum, Effect
1517 of Excess Air Ratio and Temperature on NO_x Emission from Grate
1518 Combustion of Biomass in the Staged Air Combustion Scenario, Energy
1519 & Fuels 25 (2011) 4643–4654. doi:10.1021/ef200714d.

- 1520 [69] N. Mantananont, S. Patumsawad, Particulate matter and gaseous
1521 emission rate from combustion of Thai lignite and agricultural residues
1522 in a fixed-bed combustor, *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utili-*
1523 *zation, and Environmental Effects* 38 (2016) 478–484. doi:10.1080/
1524 15567036.2013.783655.
- 1525 [70] H. Khodaei, F. Guzzomi, G. H. Yeoh, A. Regueiro, D. Patiño, An
1526 experimental study into the effect of air staging distribution and posi-
1527 tion on emissions in a laboratory scale biomass combustor, *Energy* 118
1528 (2017) 1243–1255. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2016.11.008.
- 1529 [71] É. Trudel, W. L. H. Hallett, E. Wiens, J. D. O’Neil, M. K. Busigin,
1530 D. Berdusco, Fuel particle shape effects in the packed bed combustion
1531 of wood, *Combustion and Flame* 198 (2018) 100–111. doi:10.1016/j.
1532 combustflame.2018.09.006.
- 1533 [72] J. S. Ryan, W. L. H. Hallett, Packed bed combustion of char parti-
1534 cles: Experiments and an ash model, *Chemical Engineering Science* 57
1535 (2002) 3873–3882. doi:10.1016/S0009-2509(02)00235-X.
- 1536 [73] L. Febrero, E. Granada, A. Regueiro, J. L. Míguez, Influence of Com-
1537 bustion Parameters on Fouling Composition after Wood Pellet Burn-
1538 ing in a Lab-Scale Low-Power Boiler, *Energies* 8 (2015) 9794–9816.
1539 doi:10.3390/en8099794.
- 1540 [74] B. Rashidian, Y. M. Al-Abdeli, D. Patiño, F. G. Guzzomi, G. H.
1541 Yeoh, Effect of freeboard deflectors in the fixed bed combustion of

- 1542 biomass, *Applied Thermal Engineering* 103 (2016) 543–552. doi:10.
1543 1016/j.applthermaleng.2016.04.140.
- 1544 [75] S. Polesek-Karczewska, T. Turzyński, D. Kardaś, L. Heda, Front ve-
1545 locity in the combustion of blends of poultry litter with straw, *Fuel*
1546 *Processing Technology* 176 (2018) 307–315. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.
1547 2018.03.040.
- 1548 [76] R. Pérez-Orozco, D. Patiño, J. Porteiro, J. L. Míguez, Novel Test Bench
1549 for the Active Reduction of Biomass Particulate Matter Emissions,
1550 *Sustainability* 12 (2020) 422. doi:10.3390/su12010422.
- 1551 [77] L. R. Castro, Estudo da combustão de biomassa de eucalipto em um
1552 reator de leito fixo, doutorado, Universidade Estadual de Campinas,
1553 2018.
- 1554 [78] A. Junejo, Y. M. Al-Abdeli, J. Porteiro, Role of Primary Freeboard on
1555 Staged Combustion of Hardwood Pellets in a Fixed Bed Combustor,
1556 *BioEnergy Research* (2022). doi:10.1007/s12155-022-10504-3.
- 1557 [79] G. Archan, A. Anca-Couce, J. Gregorc, M. Buchmayr, C. Hochenauer,
1558 J. Gruber, R. Scharler, Detailed experimental investigation of the spa-
1559 tially distributed gas release and bed temperatures in fixed-bed biomass
1560 combustion with low oxygen concentration, *Biomass and Bioenergy* 141
1561 (2020) 105725. doi:10.1016/j.biombioe.2020.105725.
- 1562 [80] B. Rashidian, Y. M. Al-Abdeli, G. H. Yeoh, D. Patiño, F. Guzzomi,
1563 Methodologies for Processing Fixed Bed Combustor Data, *Combustion*

- 1564 Science and Technology 189 (2017) 79–102. doi:10.1080/00102202.
1565 2016.1193497.
- 1566 [81] H. Thunman, B. Leckner, Ignition and propagation of a reaction front
1567 in cross-current bed combustion of wet biofuels, *Fuel* 80 (2001) 473–
1568 481. doi:10.1016/S0016-2361(00)00127-7.
- 1569 [82] L. B. M. van Kessel, A. R. J. Arendsen, P. D. M. de Boer-Meulman,
1570 G. Brem, The effect of air preheating on the combustion of solid fuels on
1571 a grate, *Fuel* 83 (2004) 1123–1131. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2003.11.008.
- 1572 [83] JF. Stubington, H. Fenton, Combustion characteristics of dried and
1573 pelletized bagasse, *Combustion Science and Technology* 37 (1984) 285–
1574 299.
- 1575 [84] I. ‘Aliman, A. D. Pasek, The evaluation of experimental and numerical
1576 study of combustion process on mini traveling chain grate furnace (in-
1577 cinerator) by computational fluid dynamics method, *AIP Conference*
1578 *Proceedings* 1984 (2018) 030005. doi:10.1063/1.5046626.
- 1579 [85] Y. B. Yang, V. Nasserzadeh, J. Goodfellow, J. Swithenbank, Sim-
1580 ulation of Channel Growth in a Burning Bed of Solids, *Chemical*
1581 *Engineering Research and Design* 81 (2003) 221–232. doi:10.1205/
1582 026387603762878683.
- 1583 [86] C. Ryu, Y. B. Yang, A. Khor, N. E. Yates, V. N. Sharifi, J. Swith-
1584 enbank, Effect of fuel properties on biomass combustion: Part I.
1585 Experiments-fuel type, equivalence ratio and particle size, *Fuel* 85
1586 (2006) 1039–1046. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2005.09.019.

- 1587 [87] A. Khor, C. Ryu, Y.-b. Yang, V. N. Sharifi, J. Swithenbank, Straw
1588 combustion in a fixed bed combustor, *Fuel* 86 (2007) 152–160. doi:10.
1589 1016/j.fuel.2006.07.006.
- 1590 [88] C. Ryu, A. N. Phan, V. N. Sharifi, J. Swithenbank, Combustion of
1591 textile residues in a packed bed, *Experimental Thermal and Fluid*
1592 *Science* 31 (2007) 887–895. doi:10.1016/j.expthermflusci.2006.09.
1593 004.
- 1594 [89] M. R. Karim, J. Naser, Numerical study of the ignition front
1595 propagation of different pelletised biomass in a packed bed furnace,
1596 *Applied Thermal Engineering* 128 (2018) 772–784. doi:10.1016/j.
1597 applthermaleng.2017.09.061.
- 1598 [90] A. Elorf, I. Bakhatar, M. Asbik, B. Sarh, P. Gillon, Fixed-bed Biomass
1599 Combustor: Air Mass Flow Rate and Particles Size Effects on Ignition
1600 Front Propagation of Solid Olive Waste, *Combustion Science and Tech-*
1601 *nology* 194 (2022) 365–377. doi:10.1080/00102202.2019.1680070.
- 1602 [91] S. Varunkumar, N. K. S. Rajan, H. S. Mukunda, Single Particle and
1603 Packed Bed Combustion in Modern Gasifier Stoves—Density Effects,
1604 *Combustion Science and Technology* 183 (2011) 1147–1163. doi:10.
1605 1080/00102202.2011.576658.
- 1606 [92] J. K. Tanui, P. N. Kioni, T. Mirre, M. Nowitzki, The effect of carbon
1607 dioxide on flame propagation speed of wood combustion in a fixed bed
1608 under oxy-fuel conditions, *Fuel Processing Technology* 179 (2018) 285–
1609 295. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2018.07.010.

- 1610 [93] S. Mahapatra, S. Dasappa, Experiments and analysis of propagation
1611 front under gasification regimes in a packed bed, *Fuel Processing Tech-*
1612 *nology* 121 (2014) 83–90. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2014.01.011.
- 1613 [94] R. Friberg, W. Blasiak, Measurements of mass flux and stoichiometry
1614 of conversion gas from three different wood fuels as function of volume
1615 flux of primary air in packed-bed combustion, *Biomass and Bioenergy*
1616 23 (2002) 189–208. doi:10.1016/S0961-9534(02)00048-X.
- 1617 [95] M. Fatehi, M. Kaviany, Adiabatic reverse combustion in a packed bed,
1618 *Combustion and Flame* 99 (1994) 1–17. doi:10.1016/0010-2180(94)
1619 90078-7.
- 1620 [96] T. Rogaume, M. Auzanneau, F. Jabouille, J. C. Goudeau, J. L. Torero,
1621 The effects of different airflows on the formation of pollutants during
1622 waste incineration, *Fuel* 81 (2002) 2277–2288. doi:10.1016/S0016-
1623 2361(02)00151-5.
- 1624 [97] Y. B. Yang, H. Yamauchi, V. Nasserzadeh, J. Swithenbank, Effects of
1625 fuel devolatilisation on the combustion of wood chips and incineration
1626 of simulated municipal solid wastes in a packed bed, *Fuel* 82 (2003)
1627 2205–2221. doi:10.1016/S0016-2361(03)00145-5.
- 1628 [98] X. Zhou, J. L. Torero, J. C. Goudeau, B. Bregeon, On the Propa-
1629 gation of a Reaction Front Through a Porous Fuel in the Presence of
1630 an Opposed Forced Flow: Application to Mixtures Characteristic of
1631 Municipal Waste, *Combustion Science and Technology* 110–111 (1995)
1632 123–146. doi:10.1080/00102209508951919.

- 1633 [99] R. Sun, T. M. Ismail, X. Ren, M. A. El-Salam, Effect of ash con-
1634 tent on the combustion process of simulated MSW in the fixed bed,
1635 Waste Management 48 (2016) 236–249. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2015.
1636 10.007.
- 1637 [100] D. Sakthivadivel, S. Iniyar, Combustion characteristics of biomass fuels
1638 in a fixed bed micro-gasifier cook stove, Journal of Mechanical Science
1639 and Technology 31 (2017) 995–1002. doi:10.1007/s12206-017-0152-
1640 y.
- 1641 [101] J. Kluska, M. Ochnio, P. Kazimierski, D. Kardaś, Comparison of
1642 downdraft and updraft gasification of biomass in a fixed bed reactor,
1643 Archives of Thermodynamics 39 (2018) 59–69. doi:10.1515/aoter-
1644 2018-0029.
- 1645 [102] J. Porteiro, D. Patiño, J. L. Miguez, E. Granada, J. Moran, J. Collazo,
1646 Study of the reaction front thickness in a counter-current fixed-bed
1647 combustor of a pelletised biomass, Combustion and Flame 159 (2012)
1648 1296–1302. doi:10.1016/j.combustflame.2011.10.007.
- 1649 [103] A. Junejo, Y. M. Al-Abdeli, M. Ikhtlaq, Progress Variables to Resolve
1650 the Steady State Period in a Batch-Type Fixed Bed Combustor, Com-
1651 bustion Science and Technology 0 (2022) 1–23. doi:10.1080/00102202.
1652 2022.2150969.
- 1653 [104] V. C. Simões, Formação de NOx na combustão de rejeitos de mandioca,
1654 eucalipto, bagaço e palha de cana-de-açúcar, dissertação de mestrado,
1655 Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Campinas, Brazil, 2022.

- 1656 [105] G. Stubenberger, R. Scharler, S. Zahirović, I. Obernberger, Experimental
1657 investigation of nitrogen species release from different solid
1658 biomass fuels as a basis for release models, *Fuel* 87 (2008) 793–806.
1659 doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2007.05.034.
- 1660 [106] H. Mätzing, H.-J. Gehrman, T. Kolb, H. Seifert, Experimental
1661 and Numerical Investigation of Wood Particle Combustion in Fixed
1662 Bed Reactors, *Environmental Engineering Science* 29 (2012) 907–914.
1663 doi:10.1089/ees.2011.0556.
- 1664 [107] L. D. Smoot, P. J. Smith, *Coal Combustion and Gasification*, Springer
1665 US, Boston, MA, 1985. doi:10.1007/978-1-4757-9721-3.
- 1666 [108] T. Nussbaumer, Primary and Secondary Measures for the Reduction
1667 of Nitric Oxide Emissions from Biomass Combustion, in: A. V. Bridg-
1668 water, D. G. B. Boocock (Eds.), *Developments in Thermochemical*
1669 *Biomass Conversion: Volume 1 / Volume 2*, Springer Netherlands, Dor-
1670 drecht, 1997, pp. 1447–1461. doi:10.1007/978-94-009-1559-6_113.
- 1671 [109] O. Karlström, A. Brink, M. Hupa, Biomass Char Nitrogen Oxidation—
1672 Single Particle Model, *Energy & Fuels* 27 (2013) 1410–1418. doi:10.
1673 1021/ef301932y.
- 1674 [110] O. Karlström, M. Perander, N. DeMartini, A. Brink, M. Hupa, Role of
1675 ash on the NO formation during char oxidation of biomass, *Fuel* 190
1676 (2017) 274–280. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2016.11.013.
- 1677 [111] P. Glarborg, J. A. Miller, B. Ruscic, S. J. Klippenstein, Modeling

- 1678 nitrogen chemistry in combustion, *Progress in Energy and Combustion*
1679 *Science* 67 (2018) 31–68. doi:10.1016/j.pecs.2018.01.002.
- 1680 [112] A. Anca-Couce, P. Sommersacher, N. Evic, R. Mehrabian, R. Scharler,
1681 Experiments and modelling of NO_x precursors release (NH₃ and HCN)
1682 in fixed-bed biomass combustion conditions, *Fuel* 222 (2018) 529–537.
1683 doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2018.03.003.
- 1684 [113] G. Katsaros, P. Sommersacher, S. Retschitzegger, N. Kienzl, S. A.
1685 Tassou, D. S. Pandey, Combustion of poultry litter and mixture of
1686 poultry litter with woodchips in a fixed bed lab-scale batch reactor,
1687 *Fuel* 286 (2021) 119310. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2020.119310.
- 1688 [114] H. Zhou, A. D. Jensen, P. Glarborg, A. Kavaliauskas, Formation and
1689 reduction of nitric oxide in fixed-bed combustion of straw, *Fuel* 85
1690 (2006) 705–716. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2005.08.038.
- 1691 [115] E. Houshfar, Ø. Skreiberg, D. Todorović, A. Skreiberg, T. Løvås,
1692 A. Jovović, L. Sørum, NO_x emission reduction by staged combus-
1693 tion in grate combustion of biomass fuels and fuel mixtures, *Fuel* 98
1694 (2012) 29–40. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2012.03.044.
- 1695 [116] L. F. Polonini, D. Petrocelli, A. M. Lezzi, The Effect of Flue Gas Recir-
1696 culation on CO, PM and NO_x Emissions in Pellet Stove Combustion,
1697 *Energies* 16 (2023) 954. doi:10.3390/en16020954.
- 1698 [117] M. A. Gómez, R. Martín, S. Chapela, J. Porteiro, Steady CFD combus-
1699 tion modeling for biomass boilers: An application to the study of the

- 1700 exhaust gas recirculation performance, *Energy Conversion and Man-*
1701 *agement* 179 (2019) 91–103. doi:10.1016/j.enconman.2018.10.052.
- 1702 [118] D. Shin, S. Choi, The combustion of simulated waste particles in a fixed
1703 bed, *Combustion and Flame* 121 (2000) 167–180. doi:10.1016/S0010-
1704 2180(99)00124-8.
- 1705 [119] X. Meng, R. Sun, T. M. Ismail, M. A. El-Salam, W. Zhou, R. Zhang,
1706 X. Ren, Assessment of primary air on corn straw in a fixed bed com-
1707 bustion using Eulerian-Eulerian approach, *Energy* 151 (2018) 501–519.
1708 doi:10.1016/j.energy.2018.03.081.
- 1709 [120] P. Sommersacher, T. Brunner, I. Obernberger, Fuel indexes: A novel
1710 method for the evaluation of relevant combustion properties of new
1711 biomass fuels, *Energy and Fuels* 26 (2012) 380–390. doi:10.1021/
1712 ef201282y.
- 1713 [121] H. Wiinikka, R. Gebart, The influence of fuel type on particle emissions
1714 in combustion of biomass pellets, *Combustion Science and Technology*
1715 177 (2005) 741–763. doi:10.1080/00102200590917257.
- 1716 [122] H. Wiinikka, R. Gebart, C. Boman, D. Bostrom, A. Nordin, M. Ohman,
1717 High-temperature aerosol formation in wood pellets flames: Spatially
1718 resolved measurements, *Combustion and Flame* 147 (2006) 278–293.
1719 doi:10.1016/j.combustflame.2006.08.009.
- 1720 [123] H. Wiinikka, R. Gebart, C. Boman, D. Boström, M. Öhman, Influence
1721 of fuel ash composition on high temperature aerosol formation in fixed

- 1722 bed combustion of woody biomass pellets, *Fuel* 86 (2007) 181–193.
1723 doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2006.07.001.
- 1724 [124] P. Sommersacher, T. Brunner, I. Obernberger, N. Kienzl, W. Kanzian,
1725 Combustion related characterisation of Miscanthus peat blends ap-
1726 plying novel fuel characterisation tools, *Fuel* 158 (2015) 253–262.
1727 doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2015.05.037.
- 1728 [125] E. Pettersson, F. Lindmark, M. Ohman, A. Nordin, R. Westerholm,
1729 C. Boman, Design changes in a fixed-Bed pellet combustion device:
1730 Effects of temperature and residence time on emission performance,
1731 *Energy & Fuels* 24 (2010) 1333–1340. doi:10.1021/ef901023f.
- 1732 [126] M. Horttanainen, J. Saastamoinen, P. Sarkomaa, Operational Limits
1733 of Ignition Front Propagation against Airflow in Packed Beds of Dif-
1734 ferent Wood Fuels, *Energy & Fuels* 16 (2002) 676–686. doi:10.1021/
1735 ef010209d.
- 1736 [127] M. Rhodes, Particle Size Analysis, in: *Introduction to Particle*
1737 *Technology*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2008, pp. 1–28. doi:10.1002/
1738 9780470727102.ch1.
- 1739 [128] W. Hallett, B. Green, T. Machula, Y. Yang, Packed bed combustion
1740 of non-uniformly sized char particles, *Chemical Engineering Science* 96
1741 (2013) 1–9. doi:10.1016/j.ces.2013.02.070.
- 1742 [129] Q. Meng, X. Chen, C. Bu, J. Ma, Experimental study on the controlled
1743 air oxidation of sawdust in a packed-bed reactor, *Korean Journal of*

- 1744 Chemical Engineering 29 (2012) 534–539. doi:10.1007/s11814-011-
1745 0201-7.
- 1746 [130] S. Varunkumar, N. K. S. Rajan, H. S. Mukunda, Universal Flame
1747 Propagation Behavior in Packed Bed of Biomass, Combustion Science
1748 and Technology 185 (2013) 1241–1260. doi:10.1080/00102202.2013.
1749 782297.
- 1750 [131] R. Razuan, Q. Chen, X. Zhang, V. Sharifi, J. Swithenbank, Pyrolysis
1751 and combustion of oil palm stone and palm kernel cake in fixed-bed
1752 reactors, Bioresource Technology 101 (2010) 4622–4629. doi:10.1016/
1753 j.biortech.2010.01.079.
- 1754 [132] J. F. Pérez, A. Melgar, P. N. Benjumea, Effect of operating and design
1755 parameters on the Gasification/Combustion process of waste biomass
1756 in fixed bed downdraft reactors: An experimental study, Fuel 96 (2012)
1757 487–496. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2012.01.064.
- 1758 [133] L. Tao, G. Zhao, R. Sun, Q. Wang, Combustion characteristics of
1759 particles of hazardous solid waste mixtures in a fixed bed, Journal
1760 of Hazardous Materials 181 (2010) 305–314. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.
1761 2010.05.012.
- 1762 [134] J. Porteiro, D. Patiño, J. Moran, E. Granada, Study of a fixed-bed
1763 biomass combustor: Influential parameters on ignition front propaga-
1764 tion using parametric analysis, Energy & Fuels 24 (2010) 3890–3897.
1765 doi:10.1021/ef100422y.

- 1766 [135] C. Ryu, A. N. Phan, Y.-b. Yang, V. N. Sharifi, J. Swithenbank, Igni-
1767 tion and burning rates of segregated waste combustion in packed beds,
1768 Waste Management 27 (2007) 802–810. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2006.
1769 04.013.
- 1770 [136] Y. B. Yang, V. N. Sharifi, J. Swithenbank, Effect of air flow rate
1771 and fuel moisture on the burning behaviours of biomass and simu-
1772 lated municipal solid wastes in packed beds, Fuel 83 (2004) 1553–1562.
1773 doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2004.01.016.
- 1774 [137] Z. M. Čepić, B. B. Nakomčić-Smarahdakis, Experimental analysis of
1775 the influence of air-flow rate on wheat straw combustion in a fixed bed.,
1776 Thermal Science 21 (2017).
- 1777 [138] P. Nicholls, Underfeed Combustion, Effect of Preheat, and Distribution
1778 of Ash in Fuel Beds, volume 370, USGPO, 1934.
- 1779 [139] J. Royo, P. Canalís, D. Quintana, Chemical study of fly ash deposition
1780 in combustion of pelletized residual agricultural biomass, Fuel 268
1781 (2020) 117228. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2020.117228.
- 1782 [140] P. Tripathi, L. Rao, Single particle and packed bed combustion char-
1783 acteristics of high ash and high plastic content refuse derived fuel, Fuel
1784 308 (2022) 121983. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2021.121983.
- 1785 [141] E. Granada, P. Eguía, J. Antonio Comesaña, D. Patiño, J. Porteiro,
1786 Á. Saavedra, Experimental analysis of several biomass fuels: The ef-
1787 fect of the devolatilization rate on packed bed combustion, Journal of

- 1788 Renewable and Sustainable Energy 4 (2012) 053104. doi:10.1063/1.
1789 4738593.
- 1790 [142] A. Regueiro, D. Patiño, J. Porteiro, E. Granada, J. L. Míguez, Ef-
1791 fect of Air Staging Ratios on the Burning Rate and Emissions in
1792 an Underfeed Fixed-Bed Biomass Combustor, *Energies* 9 (2016).
1793 doi:10.3390/en9110940.
- 1794 [143] L. Tao, G. Zhao, R. Sun, Combustion gas and NO emission character-
1795 istics of hazardous waste mixture particles in a fixed bed, *Korean Jour-
1796 nal of Chemical Engineering* 28 (2011) 778–787. doi:10.1007/s11814-
1797 010-0421-2.
- 1798 [144] M. Buchmayr, J. Gruber, M. Hargassner, C. Hochenauer, Experimen-
1799 tal investigation of the primary combustion zone during staged com-
1800 bustion of wood-chips in a commercial small-scale boiler, *Biomass and
1801 Bioenergy* 81 (2015) 356–363. doi:10.1016/j.biombioe.2015.07.016.
- 1802 [145] J. Royo, P. Canalís, D. Quintana, M. Díaz-Ramírez, A. Sin, A. Rezeau,
1803 Experimental study on the ash behaviour in combustion of pelletized
1804 residual agricultural biomass, *Fuel* 239 (2019) 991–1000. doi:10.1016/
1805 j.fuel.2018.11.054.
- 1806 [146] A. Regueiro, D. Patiño, E. Granada, J. Porteiro, Experimental study
1807 on the fouling behaviour of an underfeed fixed-bed biomass combustor,
1808 *Applied Thermal Engineering* 112 (2017) 523–533. doi:10.1016/
1809 j.applthermaleng.2016.10.105.

- 1810 [147] T. Nussbaumer, Combustion and Co-combustion of Biomass: Funda-
1811 mentals, Technologies, and Primary Measures for Emission Reduction,
1812 Energy & Fuels 17 (2003) 1510–1521. doi:10.1021/ef030031q.
- 1813 [148] E. Girgis, W. L. H. Hallett, Wood Combustion in an Overfeed Packed
1814 Bed, Including Detailed Measurements within the Bed, Energy & Fuels
1815 24 (2010) 1584–1591. doi:10.1021/ef901206d.
- 1816 [149] J. E. L. Rogers, Solid Fuel Combustion and Its Applications to the
1817 Incineration of Solid Refuse,, Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Tech-
1818 nology, 1973.
- 1819 [150] E. Houshfar, T. Løvås, Ø. Skreiberg, Experimental Investigation on
1820 NOx Reduction by Primary Measures in Biomass Combustion: Straw,
1821 Peat, Sewage Sludge, Forest Residues and Wood Pellets, Energies 5
1822 (2012) 270–290. doi:10.3390/en5020270.
- 1823 [151] W. Zhao, Z. Li, G. Zhao, F. Zhang, Q. Zhu, Effect of air preheating
1824 and fuel moisture on combustion characteristics of corn straw in a fixed
1825 bed, Energy Conversion and Management 49 (2008) 3560–3565. doi:10.
1826 1016/j.enconman.2008.07.006.
- 1827 [152] M. van Blijderveen, E. M. Gucho, E. A. Bramer, G. Brem, Spontaneous
1828 ignition of wood, char and RDF in a lab scale packed bed, Fuel 89
1829 (2010) 2393–2404. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2010.01.021.
- 1830 [153] L. Vorotinskienė, R. Paulauskas, K. Zakarauskas, R. Navakas,
1831 R. Skvorčinskienė, N. Striūgas, Parameters influencing wet biofuel

- 1832 drying during combustion in grate furnaces, *Fuel* 265 (2020) 117013.
1833 doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2020.117013.
- 1834 [154] A. H. Mahmoudi, M. Markovic, B. Peters, G. Brem, An experimental
1835 and numerical study of wood combustion in a fixed bed using Euler–
1836 Lagrange approach (XDEM), *Fuel* 150 (2015) 573–582. doi:10.1016/
1837 j.fuel.2015.02.008.
- 1838 [155] E. Houshfar, R. A. Khalil, T. Løvås, Ø. Skreiberg, Enhanced NO_x
1839 Reduction by Combined Staged Air and Flue Gas Recirculation in
1840 Biomass Grate Combustion, *Energy & Fuels* 26 (2012) 3003–3011.
1841 doi:10.1021/ef300199g.
- 1842 [156] J. K. Tanui, P. N. Kioni, T. Mirre, M. Nowitzki, N. W. Karuri, The
1843 influence of particle packing density on wood combustion in a fixed bed
1844 under oxy-fuel conditions, *Energy* 194 (2020) 116863. doi:10.1016/j.
1845 energy.2019.116863.
- 1846 [157] J. V M, M. K. Ambatipudi, V. S, The Phenomenon of Flame Jump in
1847 Counter-current Flame Propagation in Biomass Packed Beds – Exper-
1848 iments and Theory, *Combustion Science and Technology* 194 (2022)
1849 1199–1212. doi:10.1080/00102202.2020.1804886.
- 1850 [158] R. Pérez-Orozco, D. Patiño, J. Porteiro, A. Larrañaga, Flue Gas Recir-
1851 culation during Biomass Combustion: Implications on PM Release, *En-
1852 ergy & Fuels* 34 (2020) 11112–11122. doi:10.1021/acs.energyfuels.
1853 0c02086.

- 1854 [159] J.-H. Sung, S.-K. Back, B.-M. Jeong, J.-H. Kim, H. Choi, H.-N. Jang,
1855 Y.-C. Seo, Oxy-fuel co-combustion of sewage sludge and wood pellets
1856 with flue gas recirculation in a circulating fluidized bed, *Fuel Processing*
1857 *Technology* 172 (2018) 79–85. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2017.12.005.
- 1858 [160] C. Wang, C. Mesa, S. Bimenyimana, N. Bogonko, G. Adwek, Y. Mo,
1859 G. Asemota, C. Yuan, Y. Chen, C. Li, E. Ntagwirumugara, A. Nduwa-
1860 mungu, Effect of Varying Temperature and Oxygen on Particulate
1861 Matter Formation in Oxy-Biomass Combustion, *Energy Engineering:*
1862 *Journal of the Association of Energy Engineering* 119 (2022) 863–881.
1863 doi:10.32604/ee.2022.019248.
- 1864 [161] L. I. Díez, A. García-Mariaca, P. Canalís, E. Llera, Oxy-combustion
1865 characteristics of torrefied biomass and blends under O₂/N₂, O₂/CO₂
1866 and O₂/CO₂/H₂O atmospheres, *Energy* 284 (2023) 128559. doi:10.
1867 1016/j.energy.2023.128559.
- 1868 [162] Y. Li, H. Zhou, N. Li, C. Tao, Z. Liu, K. Cen, Experimental study
1869 of the combustion and NO emission behaviors during cofiring coal and
1870 biomass in O₂/N₂ and O₂/H₂O, *Asia-Pacific Journal of Chemical*
1871 *Engineering* 13 (2018) e2198. doi:10.1002/apj.2198.
- 1872 [163] L. I. Díez, A. García-Mariaca, E. Llera-Sastresa, P. Canalís, On the
1873 oxy-combustion of blends of coal and agro-waste biomass under dry
1874 and wet conditions, *Fuel* 365 (2024) 131265. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.
1875 2024.131265.
- 1876 [164] A. I. Escudero, M. Aznar, P. Canalís, E. Llera, L. Díez, Wet oxy-

- 1877 combustion of blends of coal and biomass, 2021. doi:10.2139/ssrn.
1878 3817253.
- 1879 [165] Y. B. Yang, C. Ryu, A. Khor, V. N. Sharifi, J. Swithenbank, Fuel
1880 size effect on pinewood combustion in a packed bed, Fuel 84 (2005)
1881 2026–2038. doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2005.04.022.
- 1882 [166] Z. Li, W. Zhao, G. Zhao, F. Zhang, Q. Zhu, Effect of Corn Stalk
1883 Length on Combustion Characteristics in a Fixed Bed, Energy & Fuels
1884 22 (2008) 2009–2014. doi:10.1021/ef700755b.
- 1885 [167] R. Sun, T. M. Ismail, X. Ren, M. A. El-Salam, Influence of sim-
1886 ulated MSW sizes on the combustion process in a fixed bed: CFD
1887 and experimental approaches, Waste Management 49 (2016) 272–286.
1888 doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2015.12.019.
- 1889 [168] Y. Rahib, T. Boushaki, B. Sarh, J. Chaoufi, A. Ihlal, S. Bonammy,
1890 E. Abdallah, Combustion Analysis of Fixed Beds of Argan Nut Shell
1891 (ANS) Biomass in a Batch Type Reactor, in: 2019 7th International
1892 Renewable and Sustainable Energy Conference (IRSEC), 2019, pp. 1–7.
1893 doi:10.1109/IRSEC48032.2019.9078217.
- 1894 [169] X. Meng, R. Sun, T. M. Ismail, W. Zhou, X. Ren, R. Zhang, Parametric
1895 studies on corn combustion characteristics in a fixed bed: Primary air
1896 flow rate and different corn lengths, Applied Thermal Engineering 126
1897 (2017) 702–716. doi:10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2017.07.197.
- 1898 [170] N. T. M. Duffy, J. A. Eaton, Investigation of factors affecting chan-
1899 nelling in fixed-bed solid fuel combustion using CFD, Combustion and

- 1900 Flame 160 (2013) 2204–2220. doi:10.1016/j.combustflame.2013.04.
1901 015.
- 1902 [171] W. Zhao, Z. Li, D. Wang, Q. Zhu, R. Sun, B. Meng, G. Zhao, Com-
1903 bustion characteristics of different parts of corn straw and NO for-
1904 mation in a fixed bed, *Bioresource Technology* 99 (2008) 2956–2963.
1905 doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2007.06.030.
- 1906 [172] T. Kolb, S. Bleckwehl, H.-J. Gehrman, H. Seifert, Characterisa-
1907 tion of combustion behaviour of refuse derived fuel, *Journal of the*
1908 *Energy Institute* 81 (2008) 1–6. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.1179/
1909 174602208X269526.